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Beyond Imperfect Match: Silicon/Graphite Hybrid Anodes for High-Energy-Density Lithium-Ion Batteries

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ABSTRACT

Silicon/graphite (Si/Gr) anodes, integrating Si's ultrahigh specific capacity with Gr's structural stability and electrical conductivity, have emerged as the most promising high-capacity systems for next-generation lithium-ion batteries (LIBs). The synergy between Si and Gr enables a balance between energy density, cycling stability, and manufacturability, already demonstrated in commercial cells. However, Si undergoes a large volume expansion of up to 300% during lithiation/delithiation, causing particle fracture, pulverization, electrode collapse, and unstable solid–electrolyte interface formation, which accelerates capacity fading. Although Gr can alleviate stress and maintain conductivity, mismatched electrochemical kinetics and mechanical properties between Si and Gr lead to heterogeneous lithiation and complex interfacial evolution, posing major engineering challenges. This review highlights recent advances in the mechanistic understanding and engineering optimization of Si/Gr anodes, emphasizing failure modes originating from both individual component degradation and interfacial coupling. The roles of advanced characterization and multiscale modeling in revealing volume effects and interfacial dynamics are discussed. Building on these insights, optimization strategies such as nanoscale structuring, interfacial engineering, buffered conductive frameworks, gradient architectures, electrode design, and pre-lithiation are summarized. A comprehensive understanding of expansion, fracture, and pulverization mechanisms is crucial for designing durable, high-energy-density Si/Gr anodes for long-life LIBs.

1 | Introduction

Since Sony Corporation unveiled the first commercial lithium-ion battery (LIB) in 1991 [1–4], this electrochemical technology has evolved into the cornerstone of portable electronics, electric mobility, and stationary energy storage infrastructures [5–8]. The proliferation of such applications has imposed ever more stringent performance metrics on LIBs, encompassing extended calendar and cycle lifetimes, heightened operational safety, and the simultaneous attainment of both high power and energy

densities [9–12]. Among the numerous determinants of energy density, the anode plays a pivotal role by fundamentally constraining the attainable performance envelope of the cell [13–19]. Graphite (Gr), as the incumbent commercial anode, accommodates lithium (Li) through intercalation into its layered lattice, thereby affording outstanding cycling stability and a low working potential. However, its theoretical capacity is intrinsically capped at 372 mAh g⁻¹ (LiC₆), which has emerged as a critical bottleneck stifling further breakthroughs in the gravimetric and volumetric energy densities of advanced LIBs [20–23].

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FIGURE 1 | Structural and electrochemical compatibility between Si and Gr in hybrid anodes.

Silicon (Si) offers an ultrahigh theoretical capacity of approximately 3579 mAh g⁻¹ (Li₁₅Si₄), nearly an order of magnitude greater than that of Gr [24], together with a suitably low lithiation potential. Despite these intrinsic advantages, Si undergoes dramatic volumetric expansion of up to ~300% during lithiation/delithiation, accompanied by the formation of an unstable solid–electrolyte interface (SEI) and rapid structural degradation [25]. These phenomena severely compromise its cycling stability and remain major obstacles to commercialization. To mitigate these issues, a wide range of strategies has been pursued, including morphology engineering with nano Si and architected structures [26, 27], the development of advanced electrolytes [28, 29], as well as improved binder systems and pre-lithiation techniques [30, 31]. Although notable progress has been achieved, large-scale implementation of Si anodes remains profoundly challenging.

Against this backdrop, hybrid anodes have emerged as a pragmatic compromise [32], achieving a balance between energy density and cycling stability, and have already entered initial stages of commercialization [33, 34]. By harnessing the complementary advantages of both constituents, these hybrids integrate the structural robustness imparted by Gr with the ultrahigh specific capacity of Si. For instance, cells incorporating 5% and 9% Si have achieved volumetric energy densities of 700 and 1043 Wh L⁻¹, respectively [35, 36]. Figure 1 illustrates the intrinsic properties and electrochemical behaviors of Gr and Si. From a materials perspective, Si is a semiconductor with intrinsically low electronic conductivity and sluggish Li-ion diffusivity at room temperature. From an electrochemical standpoint, the lithiation mechanism of Si fundamentally differs from that of Gr, underscoring both complementarity and incompatibility. These distinctions provide the rationale for the design of Si/Gr hybrid anodes, in which Gr serves as a conductive and structural scaffold, while Si contributes high specific capacity.

Over the past two decades, significant progress has been achieved in the development of Si/Gr hybrid anodes [37]. Table 1 systematically summarizes the electrochemical performance of representative Si/Gr (Si/C) anodes with different structural designs and compositions, highlighting the evolution from early physical mixtures to sophisticated engineered architectures. The earliest attempts primarily relied on simple mechanical blending, in which Si powders were directly mixed with Gr to fabricate hybrid electrodes [38–40]. While this approach offered facile processing and low cost, the pronounced disparities between Si and Gr in terms of volumetric changes, intrinsic conductivity, and lithiation kinetics frequently resulted in highly heterogeneous lithiation within the electrode. Such nonuniform reactions inevitably induce stress concentration, particle fracture, and rapid capacity fading, thereby confining the cycle life of these mechanically mixed hybrids.

To overcome the heterogeneity inherent in mechanical blending, researchers progressively shifted toward the design of engineered hybrid architectures [88–90]. Representative strategies include: (i) decorating Gr surfaces with nano Si to shorten Li-ion diffusion pathways and enhance interfacial contact; (ii) applying carbon coatings to improve the electrical conductivity and stabilize the SEI [91, 92]; and (iii) constructing gradient electrode architectures that optimize the spatial distribution along the electrode thickness, thereby mitigating the mechanical and electrochemical mismatches during charge/discharge [93, 94]. These structural innovations not only markedly improved the compatibility between Si and Gr but also extended the cycling lifetime to a certain extent, thus laying an essential foundation for the large-scale implementation of hybrid anodes.

Meanwhile, advances in characterization and modeling methodologies have further propelled progress in this field. With the aid of in situ/operando observation techniques [103], researchers

TABLE 1 | Electrochemical performance of representative Si/C hybrid anodes.

Active materials	Method and capacity (mAh g ⁻¹)	Cycling performance (mAh g ⁻¹)	Refs.
SiO@C/Gr	Pitch coating + ball milling (600)	90.7% @ 100th	[41]
SiO _x /Gr (15:85)	Mix (529.1)	523 @ 36th	[42]
7Gr-3SiO-LiPAA-SWCNT	Mix (746, 0.1C)	95% @ 2C vs. 1C	[43]
SiO _x : Gr = 6.9:93.1	Mix (440)	70% @ 200th	[44]
n-Si/SiO _x /Gr	High-energy mechanical milling (1002)	710 @ 100th (70%)	[45]
Gr/SiO _x	Mix (600)	50.5% @ 100th	[46]
SiO/Gr/C = 2/2/1	Ball-milled Gr, mix, (907.1)	850 @ 100 mA g ⁻¹ @100th	[47]
SiO/Gr	Pyrolytic carbon coating, mix (540, 0.2C)	440 @ 0.8C @ 500th	[48]
MSG-20 (SiO _x 20 wt%)	Mix, wet crosslinking (526.6)	89% @ 100th	[49]
SiO/SG/C (SiO 30wt%)	Ball milling, spray granulation (665)	385 @ 3 A g ⁻¹ 442 @ 1 A g ⁻¹ @ 300th	[50]
SNG/H-SiO _x @C	Etching, spraying, carbonization (465)	93% @ 0.5C @ 500th	[51]
N-doped carbon@Si/CNTs/N-rGO	Uniformly anchored N-doped carbon@Si nanoparticles in 3D N-doped graphene-CNT network via electrostatic interactions (1089)	1089 @ 1 A g ⁻¹ @ 500th 606 @ 2 A g ⁻¹ @ 300th	[52]
n-SiO _x @HC	Silanol-alkoxy condensation; SiO _x chemically incorporated into HC (648)	98% @ 10C @ 100th	[53]
SiO _x /Gr/C hybrid	Ball-milling, annealing; SiO _x chemically bonded to carbon via C—O—Si linkages (1482)	700 @ 1 A g ⁻¹ @ 500th	[54]
20% Super P/SiO _x	SP used to replace Gr Physical mix (1755.5)	79.33% @ 0.5C @ 50th elevation of the Li ⁺ insertion potential	[55]
Binder-free SiO _x /C	Cryo-milled SiO _x with lignin in DMF; binder-free carbonization route (1475)	900 @ 0.2 A g ⁻¹ @ 250th	[56]
SiO _x @C	rotating CVD, C ₂ H ₂ as carbon source (1400)	1116.8 @ 0.5C @ 140th	[57]
Carbon cryogel-SiO	Sol-gel polymerization, freeze drying, carbonization; SiO _x ball-milled into carbon cryogel (685)	539 @ 0.1 A g ⁻¹ @ 30th	[58]
SiO _x /CNT	ZIF-67 grown on SiO _x ; CNTs formed by carbothermal reduction and catalysis (1533)	599.6 @ 0.5 A g ⁻¹ @ 500th	[59]
Gr-Si-PAH0.2Na0.8	Mix with partially neutralized poly (acrylic acid) binder (1000)	99% @ 100th	[60]
Pitch-coated Si/Gr	Chemical dealloying, pitch coating, and carbonization with Gr (1165.1, 100 mA g ⁻¹)	764.2 @ 0.5 A g ⁻¹ @ 100th	[61]
HC-coated n-Si/Gr	Hydrothermal carbonization of a sugar-based precursor on n-Si/Gr (878.6)	84.1% @ 0.2C @ 150th	[62]
Gr@ZnO-Si-C	Liquid phase self-assembly synthesis, annealing treatment (1718)	1150 @ 0.6 A g ⁻¹ @ 1000th	[63]
n-Si@G-C	Microwave-induced carbothermal shock to anchor n-Si on Gr (500.8)	71.3 % @ 3C @ 300th	[64]
Gr@Si@C	Thin Si nanolayers on edge-exposed Gr (1080)	94.3% @ 0.2C @ 100th	[65]
Si/Gr@graphene	Spray-drying (820.7)	766.2 @ 0.5 A g ⁻¹ @ 50th	[66]
Si@Gr@C	CO ₂ -etching Gr, CVD deposition Si (823)	86.15% @ 0.2C @ 200th	[67]
SiO _x @Si/Gr microspheres	Spray-drying, carbonization (690)	90.8% @ 300th 78.5% @ 500th	[68]
Graphene/Si/Gr	Dispersing n-Si onto Gr, encapsulating a hierarchical graphene scaffold (548)	90% @ 100th	[69]
Si@Gr/graphene	Solution-based controllable self-assembly of n-Si embedded in a Gr/graphene framework (572)	502.2 @ 0.8 C @ 600th	[70]

(Continues)

TABLE 1 | (Continued)

Active materials	Method and capacity (mAh g ⁻¹)	Cycling performance (mAh g ⁻¹)	Refs.
Porous Si/Gr/CNT@C	Spray drying (863.2)	81.3% @ 0.2C @ 100th	[71]
Si@Gr	CVD process with a scalable furnace (534)	96% @ 0.1C @ 100th	[36]
CNTs-Si-CNTs	CNT arrays (AAO template) infused with Si nanoparticles via pressure-driven CVD (1320)	1310 @ 0.1 A g ⁻¹ @ 100th 1050 @ 1 A g ⁻¹ @ 500th	[72]
n-Si@C/CNT	Rice-husk-derived n-Si; 3D C-hybridized hierarchical hybrid; assembled by electrostatic interaction + hydrothermal treatment + calcination (989.5)	345 @ 3C 0.035% per cycle @ 3C @ 1000th	[73]
Si-GO@CNT	Multi-point Si—O—C bonding; CNT-reinforced GO-Si network (1980)	1223.4 @ 100th 965.9 @ 1 A g ⁻¹ @ 200th 753 @ 3C	[74]
SiPAC/CNT	PANI-coated n-Si + super-aligned CNTs; electrostatic assembly; carbonization of PANI (1302)	1046.6 @ 0.4 A g ⁻¹ @ 200th	[75]
Si/MWCNT@C	Spray-dried Si/MWCNT spheres; sucrose + CMC as carbon framework (670)	536.6 (80.5%) @ 1 A g ⁻¹ @ 300th	[76]
C-coated Si/rGO/CNT	Polymer solution method; uniform Si NP and GO distribution in carbon matrix	2700 @ 0.13 A g ⁻¹ 1311 (70%) @ 2.6 A g ⁻¹ @ 900th	[77]
Si@CNT + MOF-derived porous C	CNT intertwined on Si; ZIF-67-derived porous carbon shell after carbonization	732 @ 2 A g ⁻¹ 72.3% @ 1 A g ⁻¹ @ 100th	[78]
Si NP@C@CNT	Citric-acid-derived carbon interlayer separating the Si core and CNT framework	1055.1 @ 0.5 A g ⁻¹ @ 300th 809.9 @ 5 A g ⁻¹ 885.3 (85.9%) @ 1 A g ⁻¹ @ 1000th	[79]
Si@HC, 20 wt% n-Si	In situ polymer-derived porous carbon coating nano-Si (1037)	1037 @ 0.1 A g ⁻¹ 72.07% @ 0.6 A g ⁻¹ @ 100th	[80]
Si@C@CNT@C	Si-PANI+CNT-PANI polymerization; carbon coating on Si-CNT after microwave heat treatment.	4162 @ 1th ~1000 @ 0.42 A g ⁻¹ @ 150th	[81]
Carbon-coated Si-CNT	Pitch infiltration + pyrolysis; uniform Si NP distribution; CNT framework via carbonization (1647)	1209 @ 1 A g ⁻¹ @ 200th	[82]
Si@CA@P	Citric-acid polymer coating forming porous + compact carbon layers (600)	86.9 % @ 0.5 A g ⁻¹ @ 100th	[83]
Si/HC (37.5% Si)	Biomass-derived HC; activation-free synthesis with chitosan binder (900)	800 @ 1 A g ⁻¹ @ 100th	[84]
n-Si/C nanofibers	Surface modification, electrostatic assembly, heat-crosslinking; carbonization (1477)	1371.4 @ 0.1 A g ⁻¹ @ 100th	[85]
Si@C fibers	Magnesiothermic reduction, electrospinning (1960)	1442 @ 1 A g ⁻¹ @ 800th	[86]
Si@C nanofibers	SiO _x dispersed in PAN; electrospun into necklace-like nanofibers (1422)	710 @ 0.5 A g ⁻¹ @ 200th	[87]

are now able to directly capture volumetric evolution and phase transformations of electrodes during charge/discharge cycling, thereby elucidating the kinetic origins of heterogeneous lithiation [104, 105]. In parallel, multi-physics simulations, including electrochemical–mechanical coupling frameworks and multi-scale modeling approaches, have provided quantitative insights into stress evolution, current density distribution, and interfacial reaction dynamics, offering a deeper understanding of the failure mechanisms in hybrid anodes during cycling [106, 107]. As these advanced tools mature, the research paradigm is shifting from traditional, empirically driven “black-box” optimization toward mechanism-guided rational design, thereby opening new avenues for the engineering development of Si/Gr hybrid anodes.

As outlined in Figure 2, the research trajectory of Si/Gr anodes has evolved from early physical mixtures to advanced hybrid architectures and, more recently, to integrated experimental–computational approaches. These advances underscore both the promise and the persisting challenges of Si/Gr hybrids, highlighting the need for a systematic understanding of their lithiation mechanisms and failure processes.

This review provides a comprehensive overview of the lithiation mechanisms in Gr, Si, and their hybrid systems, with particular emphasis on how the intrinsic material properties give rise to distinct electrochemical and mechanical behaviors. We discuss diverse failure modes originating from single-component degradation as well as cross-component interactions, elucidating

Kim et al.,^[95]
Microsphere Si/Gr
 Structural engineering

2009

Ko et al.,^[36]
Microstructural Dynamics
 Operando tomography

2016

Nanda et al.,^[96]
Chemical Evolution
 Raman maps

2018

Yao et al.,^[97]
Lithiation Quantification
 Operando XRD

2019

Moon et al.,^[98]
Li⁺ Crosstalk
 Operando XRD

2021

Xu et al.,^[99]
Interactions
 Modeling

2022

Yu et al.,^[100]
SiO-Induced Interplay
 Thermal aging

2023

Kim et al.,^[101]
Reaction Dynamics
 Current decoupling, fast charging

2024

Zhang et al.,^[102]
Electrode Curvature
 Equivalent decoupling

2025

FIGURE 2 | Research trajectory of Si/Gr hybrid anodes, evolving from early physical mixtures to advanced hybrid architectures and, more recently, to integrated experimental-computational approaches. Reproduced with permission [95]. Copyright 2010, Elsevier. Reproduced with permission [36]. Copyright 2016, Springer Nature. Reproduced with permission [96]. Copyright 2018, American Chemical Society. Reproduced with permission [97]. Copyright 2019, Wiley. Reproduced with permission [98]. Copyright 2021, Springer Nature. Reproduced with permission [99]. Copyright 2022, Wiley. Reproduced with permission [100]. Copyright 2023, Springer Nature. Reproduced with permission [101]. Copyright 2024, Elsevier. Reproduced with permission [102]. Copyright 2025, Wiley.

FIGURE 3 | (a) In situ XRD pattern of the Gr anode and (b) schematic illustration of the SEI formation chemistry during the very first lithiation. Reproduced with permission [124]. Copyright 2017, International Centre for Diffraction Data. Reproduced with permission [118]. Copyright 2018, American Chemical Society. Reproduced with permission. Copyright 2019 [124], Springer Nature. (c) Bright-field TEM image of the cycled Gr electrode at the SEI/Gr interface, SAED patterns, and a schematic illustration of possible reduction in Gr crack growth. Reproduced with permission [136]. Copyright 2011, Elsevier. (d) Evolution of the (002) reflection of Gr|Li characterized by in situ XRD, SEM images of the side-view of Gr electrodes after delithiation, and a schematic illustration of the Gr anode degradation induced by Li-plating. Reproduced with permission [144]. Copyright 2011, Wiley.

their profound impacts on electrode performance and cycle life. Recent advances in state-of-the-art experimental characterization and multiscale computational approaches are also examined, highlighting their critical roles in uncovering the heterogeneous lithiation kinetics and interfacial evolution processes of hybrid

anodes. Building on these insights, we summarize optimization strategies at both the material and electrode levels, including nanoscale structural engineering, interfacial modification, electrode architecture design, and pre-lithiation techniques. Finally, we identify the key challenges that remain unresolved and

outline future research directions, aiming to provide mechanistic guidance for the rational design of Si/Gr hybrid anodes and to accelerate their practical deployment in high-energy-density, long-life LIBs.

2 | Comparative Analysis of Pure and Hybrid Anodes

The comparison between pure and hybrid anodes is of central importance for understanding the performance and stability of Si/Gr anodes. Pure anodes provide clear mechanistic insights into lithiation behavior, interfacial chemistry, and degradation pathways, serving as essential model systems for fundamental studies. In contrast, hybrid anodes combine multiple active materials, introducing new interactions that can lead to both synergistic benefits and antagonistic effects. These differences shape not only the electrochemical responses of the electrodes but also their long-term cycling stability. This section emphasizes three main aspects: (i) the mechanistic features and failure modes of single-component anodes; (ii) the coupled electrochemical and mechanical behavior in Si/Gr blends; and (iii) the unique degradation and stabilization pathways that emerge in hybrid systems. Such a comparative framework highlights the distinctive characteristics of hybrid anodes and provides a foundation for rational design strategies.

2.1 | Pure Anode Materials

Pure anode materials are the most extensively studied systems in LIB research. In these electrodes, a single active component, typically Si or Gr, dominates the lithiation/delithiation process, resulting in electrochemical responses that are straightforward to analyze and interpret. Studies of pure Gr and pure Si have enabled researchers to uncover fundamental processes such as Li storage mechanisms, phase transitions, interfacial evolution, and structural degradation during cycling. These investigations reveal the intrinsic limitations of pure systems, including the restricted capacity of Gr and the severe volume expansion of Si. Such challenges serve as a key motivation for the development of hybrid anodes, which aim to combine the advantages of different materials while mitigating their weaknesses. Understanding the behavior of pure anodes, therefore, provides not only a baseline for evaluating hybrid electrodes but also a crucial reference point for guiding advanced electrode design.

2.1.1 | Lithiation Mechanism and Interfacial Evolution of Gr Anodes

Li storage in Gr proceeds through a well-established staging mechanism, in which Li ions intercalate between Gr layers to form Gr intercalation compounds (GICs) [108, 109]. The overall reaction reaches a maximum composition of LiC_6 , corresponding to a theoretical capacity of 372 mAh g^{-1} [110]. Researchers have demonstrated a sequence of ordered phases, stage IV (LiC_{24}), stage III (LiC_{18}), stage II (LiC_{12}), and finally stage I (LiC_6), that form during lithiation, each associated with distinct voltage plateaus near 0.20, 0.11, and 0.09 V vs. Li/Li^+ [111–120]. During

this process, the (002) diffraction peak of Gr progressively shifts and splits as Li intercalates, reflecting the expansion of interlayer spacing and the coexistence of multiple staging domains. At the onset of lithiation, a weak LiC_{24} phase appears, followed by the gradual emergence of LiC_{12} , while the pristine Gr reflections diminish. As lithiation approaches full capacity, the diffraction pattern is dominated by LiC_6 , with a characteristic contraction in *c*-axis spacing compared to intermediate phases, as shown in Figure 3a.

Importantly, X-ray diffraction (XRD) also reveals that these transitions are not purely equilibrium processes but are kinetically governed: under high current densities, metastable phases persist, indicating sluggish Li diffusion and local heterogeneity [121–123]. This dynamic evolution underscores that Gr lithiation is controlled by both the thermodynamic stability of staged compounds and the kinetics of ion transport within the layered host.

The organic electrolyte used in LIBs has an oxidation potential of approximately 4.7 V (vs. Li/Li^+) and a reduction potential close to 1.0 V (vs. Li/Li^+). The potential for Li intercalation into Gr ranges from 0 to 0.25 V (vs. Li/Li^+), which is lower than the reduction potential of the electrolyte. Consequently, during charging, the potential of the Gr electrode drops below the electrolyte's stability window and decomposes to form an SEI on the Gr surface [124, 125]. Electronic insulating properties of SEI prevent further electrolyte reduction on the Gr surface and hinder solvent co-intercalation, while its ionic conductivity allows Li ions to penetrate the Gr surface and provide pathways for desired ion intercalation.

Conventional carbonate-based electrolytes, particularly those containing ethylene carbonate (EC), form the SEI through reductive decomposition of solvent molecules and LiPF_6 -derived anions (Figure 3b) [126]. The resulting layer is chemically heterogeneous: an inorganic-rich inner layer, dominated by LiF and Li_2O , provides mechanical robustness and electronic insulation, while an organic-rich outer layer, mainly consisting of Li alkylcarbonates, imparts flexibility and partial permeability [127–129]. This process involves multiple steps, starting with LiF nucleation at potentials above 1.0 V, followed by solvent co-intercalation, and then progressive EC reduction to produce Li ethylene monocarbonate (LEMC) as a dominant component [130]. Inorganic-rich SEIs are generally associated with enhanced long-term cycling stability, whereas extended organic-rich SEIs lead to resistive growth and accelerated aging [131, 132]. Beyond EC-derived interfaces, recent developments in super-concentrated electrolytes and weakly solvating solvents have enabled the formation of anion-derived SEI with improved ionic conductivity and enhanced fast-charging tolerance, providing promising alternatives to traditional interfacial chemistries [133–135].

Despite their structural reversibility, Gr anodes inevitably undergo degradation over extended cycling, arising from the interplay between bulk structural dynamics and interfacial instability. Repeated staging transitions generate internal stress and interlayer distortions, which can cause particle cracking and gradual loss of electrical contact. The stress induced by Li ion intercalation and deintercalation within the Gr lattice is believed

FIGURE 4 | (a) Li-Si phase diagram. Reproduced with permission [167]. Copyright 2009, Springer. (b) Si electrochemical lithiation and delithiation curves at room temperature and high temperature. Reproduced with permission [145]. Copyright 2012, Elsevier. (c) Operando measurement of the Si (111) Bragg reflection during the first two cycles. Reproduced with permission [146]. Copyright 2017, American Chemical Society. (d) Anisotropic lateral expansion of c-Si nanopillars with three different axial orientations upon lithiation: Top-view SEM images and Li flux profiles at a representative lithiation snapshot. Reproduced with permission [159, 160]. Copyright 2011, American Chemical Society. Copyright 2012, American Chemical Society. (e) during cycling of an a-Si sphere. Reproduced with permission [161]. Copyright 2013, American Chemical Society. (f) Schematic diagram for the initial generation and evolution of the SEIs on Si electrodes. Reproduced with permission [168]. Copyright 2021, IOP Publishing. (g) Three representative failure mechanisms of Si anodes. Reproduced with permission [169]. Copyright 2017, Royal Society of Chemistry.

TABLE 2 | Crystal structure, volume per Si atom, and unit cell volume of Li–Si alloys.

Li–Si alloy	Lattice structure	Volume per Si atom	Unit cell volume	Density	Atom amount per unit cell
Si	Tetragonal	20	160.2	2.33	8
Li ₁₂ Si ₇	Orthorhombic	58	243.6	1.15	6
Li ₁₄ Si ₆	Rhombohedral	51.5	308.9	1.43	1
Li ₁₃ Si ₄	Orthorhombic	67.3	538.4	1.38	2
Li ₂₂ Si ₅	Tetragonal	82.4	659.2	1.18	16

to cause surface structural disorder through deformation of the graphene layers and breaking of C–C bonds [136]. Interlayer cracks form near the SEI/Gr. These cracks extend parallel to each other, leading to partial delamination of the Gr layers at the SEI/Gr (Figure 3c).

Additional factors can accelerate degradation: transition-metal impurities such as Mn are able to co-intercalate with Li [137], inducing local lattice stress and interlayer distortion that hinder Li-ion transport and promote structural failure. Electrolyte composition is another key determinant, as inadequate formulations, for example, propylene carbonate-based electrolytes, tend to facilitate solvent co-intercalation and exfoliation of Gr. Due to its high dielectric constant and strong molecular dipole moment, PC acts as a strong Lewis base that coordinates tightly with Li ion to form a stable solvation complex [Li⁺(PC)_n] through strong Li–O(C=O) interactions. This strong coordination results in a large desolvation energy barrier, making it difficult for Li ion to shed its solvation sheath as it approaches the Gr surface [138–143]. Consequently, solvated Li ion-PC complexes directly insert into the Gr interlayers, leading to solvent co-intercalation. Under fast-charging conditions, the failure of Gr anodes occurs more rapidly.

Electrochemical activity within Gr particles will become increasingly heterogeneous with continued cycling, as Gr intercalation compounds (e.g., LiC₁₂ and LiC₆) gradually lose their lithiation activity (Figure 3d) [144]. During this stage, dead Li and/or side reaction products accumulate on the electrode surface, severely blocking the intercalation/deintercalation pathways and thereby accelerating the loss of Li storage capability [144]. Collectively, these structural, interfacial, and electrochemical instabilities define the dominant failure modes of Gr anodes, highlighting the necessity of engineering both material microstructure and interfacial chemistry to ensure durable operation.

2.1.2 | Lithiation Mechanism and Interfacial Evolution of Si Anodes

The early exploration of Si anodes traces back to the 1970s–1980s, when researchers recognized the extremely high theoretical Li storage capacity (about 4200 mAh g⁻¹) of Si compared to Gr. From the perspective of thermodynamics, the equilibrium Li–Si binary phase diagram indicates that Si can theoretically form a sequence of crystalline Li silicides (Figure 4a), such as Li₁₂Si₇, Li₇Si₃, Li₁₃Si₄, Li₁₅Si₄, Li₂₂Si₅, structures are shown in Table 2. The

overall lithiation reaction can be simplified as:

where $x = 4.4$ corresponds to the highly lithiated Li₂₂Si₅ phase, which gives Si its theoretical capacity of 4200 mAh g⁻¹. However, in practical electrochemical conditions at room temperature, this idealized stepwise phase evolution is rarely observed.

At room temperature, a long platform will appear at 0.1 V when single-phase Si is first alloyed with Li (Figure 4b), corresponding to the phase transition process from crystalline to amorphous [145]. When the voltage is lower than 0.05 V, the amorphous Li_xSi (a-Li_xSi) alloy is transformed into crystalline Li₁₅Si₄ (c-Li₁₅Si₄). During delithiation, the c-Li₁₅Si₄ is delithiated and finally transformed into amorphous Si (a-Si). Unlike the orderly staging in Gr, Si lithiation involves breaking and reforming of Si–Si bonds, accompanied by an amorphization process beyond the first cycle.

Extensive in situ investigations have provided critical insights into the lithiation dynamics of crystalline Si (c-Si). As illustrated in Figure 4c, operando characterization by Wu et al., monitoring the Si (111) Bragg reflection over the first two cycles, reveals a stepwise attenuation of reflection intensity with cycling time, accompanied by a systematic shift in peak position, as highlighted by the black trace in the lower intensity map [146]. The typical Raman spectrum of the pristine Si electrode, acquired at a low laser power of 0.017 mW, exhibits a sharp peak (full width at half maximum, FWHM \approx 3.2 cm⁻¹) centered at 520.6 cm⁻¹, corresponding to the transverse optical (TO) and longitudinal optical (LO) phonon modes of c-Si. They found that the absolute intensity of the c-Si Raman signal dropped significantly upon lithiation but recovered (although not completely) upon delithiation. This intensity drop results from two effects: i) the amorphization of the c-Si, such as observed in the operando XRD measurements, and ii) the changes in the optical skin depth that occur upon the formation of the Li–Si alloy [146].

Further structural insights were provided by the pioneering work of Grey and co-workers [147], who combined in situ and ex situ nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) to interrogate the amorphous phase. During the first discharge, lithiation proceeds via the formation of isolated Si and Si–Si clusters, which subsequently dissociate into isolated Si atoms before crystallization ensues. Notably, the emerging crystalline phase deviates from a strict line compound; instead, it accommodates a slight Li excess. This Li-rich phase exhibits pronounced reactivity with the electrolyte,

triggering self-discharge of the Li–Si unit, accompanied by Li depletion and a concomitant increase in the open-circuit voltage [147, 148].

Beyond c-Si, a-Si is frequently deployed in the form of SiO_x -based anodes [149]. For SiO_x materials ($0 < x < 2$), lithiation involves simultaneous alloying of the Si component and irreversible reduction of oxygen, followed by alloying of the liberated Si [150, 151]. During this process, Li_2O and Li silicates are formed [152]. Although these phases are electrochemically inactive, they serve as a mechanically robust matrix that mitigates volume expansion and enhances structural integrity.

Some reports suggest that the amorphous nature or nanodomain structure of Li_4SiO_4 within the a- SiO_x matrix may impart reactivity to the Li silicate phase. The fully lithiated state of a- SiO_x consists of Li silicate and a characteristic Li_xSi environment due to metallic domains, with a relatively high Li concentration of 3.45 Li per Si, but does not undergo a phase transition to a c- $\text{Li}_{15}\text{Si}_4$ -like structure. This matrix buffers the volume expansion of active Si domains [153], suppressing crack propagation. Although the irreversible formation of Li_2O lowers the initial Coulombic efficiency (ICE), the stabilized amorphous Li–Si–O framework improves long-term cycle life. Consistent with its alloying-dominated mechanism, the voltage profiles of SiO_x exhibit smooth sloping curves rather than the distinct plateaus characteristic of c-Si, reflecting the absence of long-range phase transitions [154, 155].

One of the most consequential effects of Si lithiation is the extreme volumetric expansion, reaching nearly 300% upon full alloying [156–158]. The mechanical response, however, differs fundamentally between c- and a-Si. In crystalline nanopillars, lithiation induces striking orientation-dependent morphological transformations: $\langle 100 \rangle$, $\langle 110 \rangle$, and $\langle 111 \rangle$ pillars evolve from circular to cruciform, elliptical, and hexagonal cross-sections, respectively (Figure 4d). Notably, $\langle 111 \rangle$ and $\langle 100 \rangle$ pillars undergo axial contraction during partial lithiation, whereas $\langle 110 \rangle$ pillars exhibit elongation, a behavior linked to the collapse of (111) planes in the early lithiation stages. Despite the isotropic Li diffusivity within the lithiated shell, Li flux is preferentially accelerated along the $\langle 110 \rangle$ direction, reflecting a pronounced anisotropy in lithiation kinetics [159, 160].

In contrast, a-Si displays markedly different characteristics. Lithiation proceeds through rupture of Si–Si bonds, forming a Li_xSi phase with comparatively lower Li content than in crystalline counterparts. As a result, the overall expansion remains below the theoretical 300% threshold. Moreover, the isotropic swelling of a-Si minimizes tensile stresses, in sharp contrast to the anisotropic strain fields and mechanical instabilities characteristic of c-Si (Figure 4e) [161].

At potentials below 0.5 V vs. Li/Li^+ , persistent electrolyte reduction drives the formation of a SEI on the Si surface (Figure 4f). In sharp contrast to the relatively stable SEI on Gr, the pronounced volume fluctuations of Si repeatedly rupture the interface, exposing fresh surfaces to ongoing electrolyte decomposition [162]. This dynamic instability accelerates electrolyte depletion, induces irreversible Li trapping, and promotes SEI thickening,

ultimately undermining ICE. Additive engineering has emerged as an effective mitigation strategy: preferential decomposition of fluoroethylene carbonate yields a LiF-rich SEI with enhanced mechanical resilience and superior ionic conductivity, thereby suppressing continuous electrolyte breakdown and prolonging cycle life [163]. Yet, despite such advances, the SEI on Si remains intrinsically dynamic, its structural integrity intricately coupled to the underlying mechanical deformation of the anode [164–166].

The electrochemical cycling stability of Si anodes is intrinsically undermined by three interrelated degradation pathways, all rooted in the material's pronounced anisotropic volume expansion exceeding 300% [170, 171]. Mechanical fracture and pulverization arise as repeated cycles generate intense internal stresses, ultimately leading to particle cracking, structural disintegration, and the progressive loss of electronic percolation (Figure 4g). Concurrently, continuous rupture and reformation of the SEI sustain parasitic electrolyte decomposition, irreversibly consuming Li inventory, thickening the interface, and elevating impedance.

At the electrode scale, interfacial stresses between the active material, conductive additives, binders, and the current collector promote delamination and electrical isolation. These processes act synergistically: fracture exposes new surfaces that accelerate SEI growth, while delamination exacerbates the disconnection of already fragmented particles, together hastening capacity fade. Mitigation strategies therefore converge on suppressing anisotropic swelling and its cascading consequences [172–175], ranging from nanostructuring and the use of a-Si or orientation-tailored c-Si with more compliant expansion characteristics [176–179], to the design of advanced polymeric binders and conductive architectures [180–185], as well as electrolyte formulations and surface coatings that stabilize the SEI [186–190].

2.2 | Si/Gr Materials as Hybrid Anodes

Hybrid anodes integrating Si and Gr are designed to harness the high capacity of Si while capitalizing on the structural stability of Gr. Owing to their markedly different physical properties (Table 3) and distinct Li storage mechanisms, the electrochemical response of the hybrid cannot be regarded as a simple superposition of the two components. Instead, the heterogeneity of Si and Gr imposes a coupled lithiation process, in which the presence of one phase influences the reaction pathway of the other.

The structural evolution of Gr in SiO_x/Gr hybrids deviates significantly from that in pristine Gr. In operando XRD measurements, although both systems exhibit comparable Gr (002) peak shifts within the 23.7° – 26.4° range, the hybrid electrode sustains lower-stage intercalation phases (e.g., LiC_{18}) over an extended duration (Figure 5a–c) [194]. As direct tracking of SiO_x lithiation is hindered by its poor crystallinity [195], time-resolved analysis of Gr phase transitions provides indirect insights into SiO_x reaction kinetics. Researchers demonstrated several key features are as follows: [195] (i) unlike pristine Gr, in which diffraction peaks immediately shift upon current application, the (002) reflection of Gr in the hybrid remains unchanged for a distinct latency period before lithiation begins, (ii) the (002) reflection transiently

TABLE 3 | Comparative physical properties of representative pure anode materials [191–193].

Anode material	Gr	Nano Si	Micro Si	SiO _x
Size	5–20 μm	50–200 nm	1–10 μm	1–10 μm
SSA (m ² g ⁻¹)	1–10	50–200	1–10	1–10
Tap density (g cm ⁻³)	0.9–1.3	0.1–0.3	0.6–0.9	0.6–1.0
Electronic conductivity (S cm ⁻¹)	~10 ² –10 ³	~10 ⁻³ –10 ⁻²	~10 ⁻³ –10 ⁻²	~10 ⁻⁴ –10 ⁻³
Crystallinity	Crystalline (hexagonal, turbostratic)	Crystalline (diamond cubic)	Crystalline (diamond cubic)	Amorphous/partially crystalline
Volume expansion	~10%	~280–320	~280–320	~80–200
D _{Li+} (cm ² s ⁻¹)	10 ⁻¹⁰ –10 ⁻⁸	10 ⁻¹³ –10 ⁻¹¹	10 ⁻¹³ –10 ⁻¹¹	10 ⁻¹³ –10 ⁻¹¹

shifts to 26.0° during the initial lithiation and final delithiation stages, indicating altered staging dynamics, and (iii) the interlayer spacing remains at 3.35 Å for nearly 7 h before expanding modestly to 3.40 Å over the subsequent 4 h, a far smaller shift ($\Delta d \approx 0.05$ Å) than the 0.2 Å change observed in pristine Gr over a comparable period.

Collectively, these observations point to a sequential lithiation mechanism: Li insertion initiates preferentially in SiO_x, progresses with concurrent uptake by both SiO_x and Gr, and culminates in dominant intercalation within Gr. This interdependence underscores the fundamentally coupled nature of Li storage in hybrid Si/Gr systems.

In 2019, a crucial work by Daniel P. Abraham's group employed operando energy dispersive XRD (EDXRD) to quantitatively resolve the lithiation states of Gr within a hybrid electrode containing 15 wt% Si in Si/Gr (Figure 5d) [97]. In parallel, operando measurements conducted on a Gr-only electrode served as calibration references, enabling deconvolution of the lithiation contributions from the Gr component in the hybrid system. By integrating structural insights from XRD with coulometric data obtained from electrochemical measurements, the Li content within the Si phase could be indirectly inferred, thus allowing the determination of the fractional lithiation of both components.

For the Gr reference electrode, the evolution of peak centroids was analyzed as a function of electrode capacity normalized to the theoretical value of 372 mAh g⁻¹ (Figure 5e). The corresponding integrated intensities were used to track phase evolution during lithiation. The Li content of Gr derived from XRD analysis is commonly validated with values obtained via coulometry, using Equation 2:

$$\bar{x} = \frac{\sum_j \left(\frac{I_j^{hkl}}{m_j^{hkl} |F_j^{hkl}|^2} \right)}{\sum_j \left(\frac{I_j^{hkl}}{m_j^{hkl} x_j |F_j^{hkl}|^2} \right)} \quad (2)$$

where x_j , I_j^{hkl} , m_j^{hkl} , and F_j^{hkl} represent the fractional Li occupancy, integrated peak intensity, reflection multiplicity, and scattering factor of each phase j , respectively. Analogous features were also identified in the Si/Gr hybrid electrode (Figure 5f). By employing

the Gr lithiation profile (Figure 5e) as an internal calibration, the fractional capacities of both Gr and Si were estimated via Equation 2. Although the overall lithiation sequence was similar to that of the Gr-only electrode, a key distinction was that Gr lithiation in the hybrid became pronounced only when the electrode potential decreased below 0.20 V vs. Li/Li⁺. At the end of lithiation, the Si/Gr electrode cannot recover its theoretical capacity, suggesting incomplete utilization of certain Si particles, indicative of particle isolation effects, even under slow cycling conditions.

In contrast to lithiation, delithiation initiated immediately from the Gr phase (Figure 5f). Li extraction from the Si component occurs only after the electrode potential rises above a certain threshold voltage, which depends on the Si/Gr content ratio. Thus, in n-Si/Gr hybrid anodes, lithiation initially favors Si alloying down to 0.20 V (the onset potential for Gr lithiation), below which concurrent lithiation of both components occurs. During delithiation, Li is first extracted from the Gr phase, followed by progressive Li removal from the Si phase at higher potentials (>0.22 V, corresponding to the Gr delithiation potential).

In micro-Si/Gr hybrids, where both components are micron-sized particles, operando synchrotron XRD combined with electrochemical analysis can provide key insights into the coupled lithiation dynamics of the two phases (Figure 5g–i) [196]. In Si-rich hybrids, the majority of capacity is delivered by Si alloying at higher potentials, while Gr contributes significantly only at lower voltages, reflecting delayed stage transitions and suppressed lithiation kinetics. Importantly, the delithiation pathway is not a simple reversal of lithiation: Gr undergoes rapid early deintercalation, whereas capacity recovery at higher voltages is dominated by sequential dealloying of amorphous Li_xSi phases.

At higher Si loadings, Gr lithiation is further hindered [197], with polarization behavior of Gr governed less by nominal current density than by the interplay with Si, underscoring the dominance of Si/Gr interactions in shaping electrochemical response. Collectively, these observations highlight the pronounced “crosstalk” between the two phases, whereby Si alloying not only dictates the overall voltage profile but also constrains the kinetics and structural evolution of Gr.

In contrast to the relatively homogeneous, diffusion-controlled lithiation of Gr, Si domains in mixed anodes exhibit far more

FIGURE 5 | Lithiation behavior of hybrid anodes: (a–c) Comparison of lithiation behavior of pure Gr(a), SiO_x/Gr(b) anode, and time dependence of the distance between interlayers of Gr (c upper) and Gr-SiO_x (c low). Reproduced with permission [194]. Copyright 2013, Elsevier. (d–f) Comparison of the lithiation behavior of pure Gr and n-Si/Gr anode. Reproduced with permission [97]. Copyright 2019, Wiley. (g–i) Comparison of lithiation behavior of micro-Si/Gr with different Si ratios. Reproduced with permission [196]. Copyright 2024, Wiley.

complex structural evolution. This process involves amorphization and the formation of core-shell structures (Figure 6a,b), comprising a crystalline core surrounded by an expanding amorphous shell [198]. Minor fractions of c-Li₁₅Si₄ appear only at very low potential, while overall capacity declines rapidly within the early cycles due to irreversible Li consumption and incomplete delithiation.

Progressive amorphization of c-Si occurs after the first cycle (Figure 6c), followed by lithiation dominated by the amorphous shell. Notably, the crystalline core experiences compressive strain rather than simple expansion, caused by hydrostatic pressures from the surrounding amorphous shell. Over subsequent cycles, c-Si shows only limited reversible lithiation, contributing marginally to capacity, whereas capacity fade is primarily

FIGURE 6 | (a–c) Operando XRD results for Si/Gr anodes over five cycles. Galvanostatic cycling profiles and XRD patterns (a), corresponding differential capacity-potentials (b), and analysis of the Si individual component in Si/Gr anodes (c). Reproduced with permission [198]. Copyright 2025, Wiley. (d) Visualized structural heterogeneities showing in-plane Li distribution in Si and Gr, and reveal heterogeneous lithiation during cycling and relaxation. Reproduced with permission [199]. Copyright 2023, Wiley.

driven by incomplete delithiation of a-Si, Li trapping, and SEI thickening.

Lithiation in Si/Gr hybrid anodes follows a sequential yet partially concurrent process (Figure 6d), in which both phases lithiate simultaneously during charging [199], whereas delithiation proceeds first through Gr and subsequently through Si. Distinct in-plane lithiation heterogeneities, which remain reproducible across cycles, reflect intrinsic spatially uneven reaction pathways within the hybrid electrode. Moreover, opposite lithiation gradients are observed for Gr and Si across the elec-

trode thickness, underscoring their contrasting electrochemical dynamics.

2.3 | Interfacial Behaviors of Si/Gr Hybrid Anodes

Beyond the individual lithiation behaviors of each component, hybrid anodes exhibit unique inter-component interactions. These include Li crosstalk between Si and Gr, heterogeneous current distribution, and mismatched lithiation kinetics. While pristine Gr typically displays depth-dependent lithiation

FIGURE 7 | (a–c) Asymmetric behavior in a Si/Gr electrode. Color and volume change during cycles (a), in situ Raman spectroscopy during lithiation (b), and the phase distribution of colors in Gr and Si/Gr (c). Reproduced with permission [105]. Copyright 2023, Elsevier. (d, e) Li-ion trapping in Si due to crosstalk between Si and Gr. Reproduced with permission [98]. Copyright 2021, Springer Nature. (f) Overpotential ΔV values plotted with corresponding Si NP contents for lithiation/delithiation. (g) Li-ion diffusion coefficients versus voltage plots from lithiation/delithiation of Si/Gr anodes. Reproduced with permission [201]. Copyright 2025, Elsevier.

heterogeneity, the rapid surface diffusion of Li-ion and the additional overpotential introduced by the Si phase in hybrid electrodes can partially suppress this effect [200]. A sequential yet synergistic lithiation process occurs during the initial cycle (Figure 7a–c), in which Gr lithiation coincides with pronounced Si expansion. In subsequent cycles, however, Si begins to lithiate earlier, actively facilitating Li-ion insertion into Gr and promoting a more homogeneous lithiation profile across the hybrid

electrode [105]. Notably, Si alters the spatial distribution of Gr phase transitions, mitigating the sharp separation between red and yellow domains typically observed in Gr-only electrodes, and enabling deeper lithiation across the electrode depth. These findings highlight that Si incorporation not only modifies the kinetics of Gr lithiation but also alleviates its depth-dependent heterogeneity. Nevertheless, other studies suggest that such synergistic effects come at the expense of increasingly disordered

ionic transport and complex redistribution phenomena in hybrid electrodes.

In Si/Gr anodes, operando XRD studies by Moon et al. have revealed that at approximately 80% state of charge (SOC), Li-ion can transfer from Si to Gr, driven by potential differences between surface-localized Li_xSi and Gr [98]. However, stress-induced inhomogeneity within Si hinders Li-ion transport into the crystalline core, leaving Li trapped in mechanically constrained regions (Figure 7d,e). This “crosstalk” between Si and Gr not only governs lithiation pathways but also promotes irreversible Li retention, thereby accelerating degradation.

The composition-dependent nature of this coupling is also reflected in the electrochemical behavior. A study led by Pham et al. demonstrated that the differential capacity (dQ/dV) profiles exhibit negligible overpotential ($\Delta V < 0.003$ V) when the Si content is below 12 wt% [201], but a sharp increase at 15 wt% signals elevated kinetic barriers and an enhanced risk of Li plating at the Gr interface. This indicates blending Si with Gr generally improves Li diffusivity compared with Si-only electrodes (Figure 7f,g), yet increasing Si fraction reduces D_{Li^+} during critical phase transitions. In other words, Si primarily governs diffusion stages, while Gr dominates phase transitions; excessive Si loading, however, impairs overall Li transport and suppresses Gr utilization.

Charge redistribution between Si and Gr follows stress-relaxed lithiation pathways [199]. Gr partially delithiates from $\text{Li}_{0.8}\text{C}_6$ to $\text{Li}_{0.6}\text{C}_6$ (Figure 8a), while Si simultaneously increases its Li content, both converging toward a common equilibrium potential at 120 mV. In the depth-resolved case (Figure 8a), heterogeneity becomes evident: Li in Gr decreases from $\text{Li}_{0.8}\text{C}_6$ to $\text{Li}_{0.6}\text{C}_6$, Si near the current collector evolves from $x \approx 0.55$ to $x \approx 0.72$ in Li_xSi through stress-relaxed lithiation, and Si near the separator slightly delithiates from $x \approx 0.92$ to $x \approx 0.87$ following one of the lower-potential delithiation paths. These results demonstrate that Gr always serves as a Li donor, while Si acts as both sink and source depending on local lithiation states, confirming a generalized shuttle reaction that governs charge redistribution and homogenization in hybrid Si/Gr anodes.

Current distribution measurements reveal a persistent imbalance between Si and Gr, which becomes more pronounced under high-rate and elevated-temperature conditions [202]. Table 4 summarizes the capacity (current) contribution in typical Si/C hybrid anodes. At low rates, Gr initially dominates lithiation, but its current contribution rapidly decays, allowing Si to govern reactions at low SOC (Figure 8b). As SOC increases (SOC = 0.25), lithiation proceeds through alternating contributions from Si and Gr, reflecting the superposition of their differential capacity (dQ/dV) profiles and phase-transition plateaus. Specifically, Si alloying dominates above 220 mV, while Gr becomes more active across its two-phase regions. During delithiation, the sequence is not a simple reversal; instead, distinct SOC windows emerge, with Gr prevailing at high SOC (0.65–1.0) and Si at intermediate-to-low SOC (0.05–0.5). These findings underscore the dynamic and non-symmetric current redistribution inherent to Si/Gr hybrid anodes.

Hybrid Si/Gr anodes exhibit a set of unique behaviors that cannot be captured by single-component electrodes [205]. On the beneficial side, the presence of Si can mitigate depth-dependent heterogeneity in Gr and promote more homogeneous lithiation across the electrode. At the same time, the interplay between the two phases introduces additional complexity, including Li crosstalk, kinetic overpotentials, and nonuniform current redistribution. These effects are strongly dependent on Si content, SOC, and operating conditions, and can shift the electrode response from synergistic to antagonistic. Overall, the electrochemical characteristics of hybrid anodes are governed by a delicate balance between thermodynamic driving forces and kinetic limitations, making their performance distinct from that of either pure Si or Gr anode.

2.4 | Si/Non-Gr Carbon Materials as Hybrid Anodes

The incorporation of non-Gr carbon (NGC), such as amorphous carbon (resin- or pitch-derived low-temperature carbon), carbon aerogels, and other disordered carbons, has become a defining characteristic of practical Si-based anode design. Unlike Gr, these carbons possess intrinsically disordered atomic arrangements, abundant defect sites, hierarchical porosity, and high mechanical compliance, endowing them with multifunctionality far beyond simple conductivity enhancement. Their interactions with Si, both structurally and electrochemically, critically determine the performance and durability of hybrid anodes.

The integration between Si and NGC can be achieved through several pathways, each leading to distinct interfacial chemistries and structural environments. The lithiation of NGC itself is governed by a combination of surface adsorption, defect-driven insertion, and pore-filling processes, which occur over broad potential ranges and impart pseudocapacitive contributions to the overall capacity [206]. When coupled with Si, these carbons participate in a complex competitive-cooperative lithiation relationship. During the early stages of cycling, Li tends to occupy high-surface-energy defect sites and micropores within NGC, alleviating the initial stress imposed on Si and moderating the first-cycle volume expansion. As deeper lithiation proceeds, Si becomes the principal host owing to its exceptionally high theoretical capacity, yet the presence of NGC provides a buffer reservoir that homogenizes Li distribution and reduces local lithiation extremes [207–209].

The defective, multidimensional conduction pathways within NGC additionally reduce charge-transfer resistance and facilitate both ionic and electronic transport, a benefit particularly evident in CVD-grown Si/C structures and SiO_x/NGC hybrids, where interface transport often governs electrode-level performance [210]. NGC also contributes decisively to the mechanical stability of Si hybrids. Its intrinsically low modulus and high deformability enable it to accommodate the volumetric oscillations of Si via viscoelastic deformation, thereby absorbing mechanical strain that would otherwise trigger particle fracture or intergranular cracking [211, 212].

The porous architecture of many NGC materials provides internal free volume that supports Si expansion and delays structural

FIGURE 8 | (a) Mechanism of charge dynamics in Si/Gr anodes during relaxation. Reproduced with permission [199]. Copyright 2023, Wiley. (b) Potential profiles, specific currents, and specific capacity contributions related to the competing electrochemical reactions of Si and Gr during lithiation/delithiation. Reproduced with permission [202]. Copyright 2021, Wiley.

pulverization. At the same time, the interfacial chemistry between NGC and the electrolyte tends to yield more inorganic-rich and mechanically robust SEIs, which are less prone to repeated rupture than those forming directly on Si. These stabilized int help suppress continuous electrolyte decomposition and limit the formation of thick, resistive SEIs that can accelerate impedance growth [213, 214]. Through these effects, NGC moderates both the mechanical and chemical instability that typically undermines high-Si-content electrodes.

During prolonged cycling, the interactions between Si and NGC continue to evolve. The extensive interfacial contact promotes rapid Li-ion transport across Si-NGC boundaries, which helps maintain uniform lithiation fronts and prevents localized hot spots of electrochemical activity [215]. Chemical reconstruction at the interface, including the progressive formation of Si-C bonding motifs or rearrangement of defective carbon domains, can further strengthen interfacial cohesion and mitigate delamination or electrical isolation of Si particles [216]. Nevertheless, failure modes such as pore coarsening, gradual debonding, and the formation of electrically inactive “dead Si” may still develop. These degradations, however, typically proceed more slowly than in pure Si because NGC dissipates mechanical stresses, maintains electrical connectivity, and stabilizes SEI chemistry over a broad range of cycling states. Table 1 lists the properties of SiO_x/NGC

and n-Si/NGC systems, mainly including amorphous carbon and functional carbonaceous materials such as CNTs and graphene.

Overall, the integration of non-Gr carbon fundamentally reshapes the lithiation behavior, interfacial chemistry, and structural resilience of Si-based anodes. Whether through nanoscale encapsulation, 3D embedding, or interfacial chemical coupling, NGC acts not only as a mechanical buffer and conductive additive but also as an active participant in Li storage and interface regulation. Its presence defines the collective electrochemical response of Si/C hybrids and represents a key enabling factor for advancing Si anodes toward practical, long-life LIBs.

3 | Failure Mechanisms and Stability Issues in Hybrid Si/Gr Anodes

The introduction of Si-based materials into Gr anodes substantially enhances energy density. However, this also introduces complex and significant effects on electrode lifespan and failure behavior. Extensive research has attributed the predominant failure mechanisms of hybrid anodes to the degradation of the Si component [195]. As discussed in Section 2, the intrinsic volume fluctuations of Si and the consequent mechanical disconnection, particle pulverization, unstable SEI, and electronic/ionic

TABLE 4 | Capacity (current) contribution in Si/Gr hybrid anodes.

Active material	Lithiation	Delithiation	Method	Refs.
n-Si/Gr (15%)	1.0–0.2 V: $\text{Li}_{\text{Si}}/\text{Li}_{\text{Gr}} = 0.96/0.04$; 0.01–0.2 V: $\text{Li}_{\text{Si}}/\text{Li}_{\text{Gr}} = 0.58/0.42$	0.01–0.22 V: $\text{Li}_{\text{Si}}/\text{Li}_{\text{Gr}} = 0$ 0.22–1.0 V: $\text{Li}_{\text{Si}}/\text{Li}_{\text{Gr}} = 0.97/0.03$	Operando EDXRD	[97]
n-Si/Gr (7%)	9.4% Li^+ transfer from Si to Gr at 81.7% SOC	Si (91.0%) and Gr (85.6%) after 250 cycles	Operando XRD	[98]
SiO_x/Gr (10%)	OCP of SiO_x exceeds Gr at SOC 7–82%		An electro-chemo-mechanical model	[99]
Si/Gr (7.14%)	>220 mV: Si-dominated 110 mV: Gr dominated 85 mV: Gr-dominated	0.65 < SOC < 1: Gr-dominated 0.05 < SOC < 0.5: Si-dominated	A model-like hybrid anode	[202]
LGM50T (SiO_x/Gr)	Si loss: 80% (0%–30% SOC), 30% (0%–100% SOC)		Post-mortem dQ/dV	[203]
SiO_x/Gr (8%)	Retention loss: 0%–30% SOC > 10%–40% SOC		Constant cycling protocol	[204]
Si/Gr (30%)	Two Gr current maxima at 0.1 and 0.06 V (~70% of total current each)	Delithiation: Gr current matches cell current until 0.2 V Si peak delithiation rate: 0.065 C (C/15) Gr peak delithiation rate: 0.19 C (C/5)	Decoupled hybrid cell	[204]
n-Si/Gr (12%)	>0.19 V: Si 38%, Gr 10% lithiation 0.19–0.1 V: Si 38%–45%, Gr 10%–45% <0.1 V: Si & Gr lithiation synchronized	Early delithiation: Gr ~90% capacity loss, Si minimal loss	Curvature changes measurement	[102]
Si/Gr (5%)	Full lithiation: $x = 0.65$ in Li_xC_6		Neutron diffraction study	[104]
Si/Gr (30%)	Capacity of Gr: 260.4 mAh g^{-1}	Gr nearly fully delithiated after ~200 min (C/5)	Operando synchrotron XRD + DC	[196]
Si/Gr (70%)	Capacity of Gr: 55 mAh g^{-1}	Gr contributes very little at initial delithiation	Operando synchrotron XRD + DC	[196]
Si/Gr	1st delithiation = 704 mAh g^{-1} , $x = 0.64$ in Li_xC_6 , $x = 3.22$ in Li_xSi ; 2nd delithiation = 707 mAh g^{-1} , $x = 0.34$ in Li_xC_6 , $x = 3.53$ in Li_xSi ; 3rd delithiation = 701 mAh g^{-1} , $x = 0.23$ in Li_xC_6 , $x = 3.68$ in Li_xSi ; 5th delithiation = 652 mAh g^{-1} , $x = 0.21$ in Li_xC_6 , $x = 3.42$ in Li_xSi ;		Operando synchrotron XRD + DC	[198]

isolation play critical roles in capacity fade [217]. The failure pathway of Si/C hybrid anodes is not completely consistent with that of pure Si electrodes. To clarify these differences, researchers have distinguished between degradation originating from the Si component alone and that arising from the coupled interaction of Si and Gr. Significant efforts have been devoted to the design of functional binders and electrolyte formulations to mitigate these issues.

3.1 | Effect of Single Components

In a comprehensive analysis, Gasteiger et al. proposed detailed degradation mechanisms for Si in hybrid electrodes [218]. Their differential capacity–voltage curves clearly indicated that, while the delithiation peak associated with Gr remained largely unchanged, the Si-rich electrodes (50 wt%) exhibited pronounced potential shifts at voltages above 0.2 V vs. Li/Li^+ after 60 cycles (Figure 9a). The disappearance of lithiation shoulders in the 0.25–0.5 V

range confirmed the incomplete lithiation of Si, which accounted for the substantial loss of reversible capacity. Moreover, during delithiation, both Gr and Si-rich electrodes showed pronounced changes at potentials >0.25 V vs. Li/Li^+ , including the characteristic peak near 0.45 V, assigned to the two-phase transition between $\text{c-Li}_{15}\text{Si}_4$ and $\text{a-Li}_x\text{Si}$ [219]. The coexistence of such two-phase boundaries was found to exacerbate local stress and accelerate particle fracture, thereby coupling structural degradation with electrochemical fading.

Their further investigations revealed that Si particle degradation dominates the early cycles, giving rise to a sigmoidal evolution of irreversible capacity. A pronounced slope maximum around the 20th cycle correlates with the onset of morphological instability, followed by a stabilization of the Si structure after 45 cycles (Figure 9b), where steady-state particle morphologies suppress further degradation. Approximately one-fifth of the lithiation capacity after 45 cycles arises from the constant-voltage step

FIGURE 9 | Single component effect. (a) dQ/dV curves of Si/Gr anodes with 20 wt% and 50 wt% Si. (b) Total irreversible capacity $\Sigma Q_{\text{irr, Si}}$ ($\text{mAh}_{\text{irr}} \text{g}^{-1}_{\text{Si}}$) normalized to the mass of Si. Reproduced with permission [218]. Copyright 2017, IOP Publishing. (c) TEM images of Si particles. Reproduced with permission [220]. Copyright 2018, IOP Publishing. (d, e) SEM cross-section images of Gr/Si anodes with different Gr components. (f) Sketch of different responses of a Gr matrix toward a volume expansion of Si in Gr/Si hybrid anodes. Reproduced with permission [221]. Copyright 2020, IOP Publishing.

at 0.01 V, suggesting the persistence of kinetically sluggish reactions [218].

Si nanoparticles, which are initially dense and crystalline (~200 nm), progressively transform into nanoporous networks after extensive cycling due to repeated dealloying (Figure 9c). This structural evolution, accompanied by up to 700% permanent volume expansion, generates high-surface-area branches stabilized by SEI deposition. The increase in interfacial area not only accelerates electrolyte decomposition but also thickens the electrode, thus coupling morphological instability with electrochemical inefficiency [220].

The size of Gr particles plays a critical role in determining the structural and electrochemical behavior of Si/Gr hybrid electrodes (Figure 9d–f). Electrodes employing smaller Gr particles promote a more homogeneous dispersion of n-Si, while larger Gr particles generate voids and local stress concentrations, ultimately weakening the electrode integrity. At higher Si contents, “inverse morphologies” emerge, in which Si forms the matrix with embedded Gr, creating heterogeneous stress distributions that compromise cycling stability [221]. Collectively, Si-induced failure in hybrid anodes primarily arises from particle fracture, detachment, and loss of electrical connectivity, compounded by accelerated SEI growth and morphological instability.

3.2 | Effect of Interactions on Si/Gr Anode Failure

In addition to degradation mechanisms intrinsic to Si, interactions between Si and Gr further complicate the failure behavior of hybrid anodes. As discussed in Section 2, Li-ion cross-talk within hybrid electrodes leads to Li trapping in the Si phase over prolonged cycling. This accumulation lowers open-circuit voltage and contributes to irreversible capacity losses (Figure 10a). The volume expansion of Si induces local stress on surrounding Gr, which in turn suppresses its lithiation via stress-driven phase transitions, thereby reducing the overall performance of both components [98]. Raman microspectroscopy studies revealed pronounced phase segregation (Figure 10b), with c-Si persisting in isolated domains even after extended cycling. This observation indicates partial electrochemical and electronic isolation of Si regions, which remain inactive and fail to participate in lithiation [96].

At intermediate Si fractions, interface-induced cascading failure has been widely reported. For instance, the incorporation of 15 wt% Si into Gr-based electrodes led to rapid disintegration of the hybrid microstructure, not as a result of Si particle fracture (Figure 10c) [222], but due to progressive capacity loss within the Gr component, attributable to the isolation of Gr domains from the conductive network. As Si expansion and cracking disrupted the electrode architecture [222], electrical contact between Gr particles was lost, resulting in electrochemically inactive lithiated Gr. Other interaction-driven effects include asynchronous (de)lithiation between SiO_x and Gr phases, which causes abnormal current localization and steep Li-ion concentration gradients (Figure 10d). This mismatch introduces severe polarization, leading to residual Li trapping within SiO_x and progressive capacity decay. Both diffusion polarization and activation overpotential contribute to

impedance heterogeneity, further aggravating electrochemical instability [223].

When discussing failure mechanisms arising from inter-component interactions, it is essential to consider the Si/Gr ratio in hybrid anodes. This ratio is particularly important, as it directly governs the balance between mechanical stress accommodation, electronic connectivity, and lithiation kinetics within the hybrid structure. In SiO_x/Gr hybrid anodes, increasing the SiO_x content leads to a reduction in the averaged lithiation rate and SOC of Gr [99], accompanied by a more pronounced SOC gradient along the electrode thickness (Figure 11a), particularly in Gr regions adjacent to SiO_x particles. In contrast, the SOC distribution within SiO_x particles remains relatively uniform.

In addition, Li plating on the anode surface can severely impact the interfacial stability and cycling performance, and the Si content strongly influences this behavior. At lower SiO_x contents, the onset of Li plating is noticeably delayed (Figure 11b). However, once the SiO_x content exceeds 8 wt%, the extent of Li plating increases sharply, leading to accelerated cell failure.

Unlike pure Si electrodes, where fracture-induced pulverization predominates, capacity fading in Si/Gr hybrids is more closely associated with mechanically induced loss of interparticle contact and the resulting increase in electronic resistance (Figure 11c). The irreversible Li consumption primarily originates from SEI formation, which remains uniformly distributed across the electrode thickness. Electrodes with higher Si content exhibit more pronounced SEI growth, adversely impacting overall cell performance. Consequently, capacity fading arises not from ionic or electronic transport limitations associated with different Si ratios, but rather from mechanically driven disconnection between Si and Gr particles and the accompanying increase in SEI accumulation (Figure 11d) [224, 225].

Furthermore, as Si content critically dictates the prevailing degradation mode, establishing an appropriate practical Si fraction is essential for controlling full-cell failure. The beneficial interaction between Si and Gr is generally observed only within a limited compositional window. At low-to-moderate Si contents (<15 wt%), the two components operate synergistically: Si contributes additional capacity without imposing excessive mechanical stress, while Gr maintains electronic continuity and provides an accommodating matrix that mitigates Si-induced strain.

As demonstrated by Gautam et al. [226], increasing Si from 10 to 15 wt% enhances both lithiation and delithiation capacities by roughly 16% while still preserving a high ICE comparable to Gr. Increasing the Si content in the low-capacity range can reduce the electrode loading and thickness, thereby shortening the Li-ion diffusion path, which is beneficial for the use of such electrodes in high-power applications, as shown in Figure 12c [227]. However, multiple studies consistently show that once the Si fraction exceeds ~25 wt%, the hybrid enters an antagonistic regime.

Wetjen et al. [218] reported that within the 20–60 wt% range, higher Si content yields progressively larger irreversible capacity

FIGURE 10 | Two-component effect. (a) Schematic of the degradation mechanism (the Li accumulation in the Si core). Reproduced with permission [98]. Copyright 2021, Springer Nature. (b) Raman maps of Si/Gr anodes. Reproduced with permission [96]. Copyright 2018, American Chemical Society. (c) Microstructural investigation, schematic of electron pathway, and XPS spectra of Si/Gr electrodes. Reproduced with permission [222]. Copyright 2019, Wiley. (d) Computation results of the SiO_x/Gr hybrid anodes. Reproduced with permission [223]. Copyright 2024, Wiley.

losses, stronger polarization, accelerated SEI accumulation, and distinct degradation phenomena including particle fracture, as shown in Figure 12a,b. Likewise, analytical electrode-density models [228] predict diminishing returns in volumetric capacity beyond ~25 wt% Si due to swelling-induced densification limits. Collectively, these findings place the synergistic–antagonistic

transition near 15–25 wt%, above which Si expansion outpaces the mechanical and conductive support provided by the Gr framework.

From a full-cell perspective, the optimal Si fraction is further constrained by stack-level mechanical and volumetric

FIGURE 11 | (a) Comparison of electrochemical behaviors among models with various SiO_x contents. (b) Evolution of the Li plating overpotential, the zoom-in image, and the Li plating amount. Reproduced with permission [99]. Copyright 2023, Wiley. (c) Illustration of the difference in the mean electron conduction path length of Si/Gr anodes with different Si/Gr ratios. Reproduced with permission [218]. Copyright 2017, IOP Publishing. (d) Li concentration profiles for Si/Gr electrodes at different DODs. Reproduced with permission [224]. Copyright 2021, IOP Publishing.

considerations. As emphasized in Kim's work [33], the practical energy density of Si-containing batteries is not primarily limited by the intrinsic capacity of Si but by the mandatory free volume required to accommodate electrode swelling. As shown in Figure 12d–i, increasing Si above ~20 wt% leads to substantial and partly irreversible thickness growth—stemming from Si breathing, cumulative SEI formation, and Li trapping—which directly reduces the permissible number of electrode stacks within a fixed cell format. Consequently, even nominally high-capacity Si-rich anodes may deliver lower cell-level energy density than Gr due to swelling-driven losses in packing efficiency.

In contrast, electrodes containing ~10 wt% Si typically offer the most balanced performance: they provide meaningful capacity enhancement while maintaining calendered density, moderate porosity (~30%), and a swelling profile compatible with high stack utilization. Within this range, Gr remains the mechanically dominant phase, enabling strain distribution and preserving percolation pathways, while Si stays below the threshold where its volumetric expansion destabilizes the hybrid. Although advanced structural designs, such as void-engineered Si/C architectures,

multi-scale carbon encapsulation, and porous or yolk-shell configurations, can extend the tolerable Si content, commercial feasibility still strongly favors formulations in which Si is a minority component. Accordingly, Si fractions near ~10 wt% consistently emerge as the most effective for maintaining the delicate balance between enhanced capacity, cell-level volumetric energy density, and long-term mechanical robustness.

Overall, the interplay between Si and Gr introduces unique degradation pathways distinct from those observed in single-component electrodes. Mechanical disconnection, interfacial stress transfer, asynchronous reaction kinetics, and current redistribution collectively accelerate capacity fade and pose critical challenges for the long-term stability of Si/C hybrid anodes.

3.3 | Effect of Structures on Si/Gr Hybrid Anode Failure

The electrochemical stability of Si/Gr hybrid anodes is governed primarily by how Si is spatially distributed, mechanically

FIGURE 12 | (a,b) Galvanostatic cycling of Si/Gr||LFP coin-cells, with different Si/Gr electrode compositions. Reproduced with permission [218]. Copyright 2017, IOP Publishing. (c) Schematic of structural changes with increasing Si content. Reproduced with permission [227]. Copyright 2025, Elsevier. (d–i) Electrode swelling (d, g) and estimated cell-level volumetric (e, h) and gravimetric (f, i) energy densities, along with the specific capacity as a function of SiO (d–f) or Si content (g–i) in the anode. Reproduced with permission [33]. Copyright 2023, Springer Nature.

buffered, and electronically connected within the hybrid framework. When evaluated under comparable electrode loading, areal capacity, and binder/conductive–additive ratios, three general structural strategies demonstrate markedly different levels of stability: (i) physically mixed or loosely aggregated Si within Gr, (ii) engineered secondary particles with partially integrated Si/C frameworks, and (iii) highly uniform nanoscale Si integration and hierarchical buffering architectures.

Under-matched specific/areal capacities, systems where Si exists as isolated aggregates within a Gr matrix typically exhibit the most severe volume expansion ($>120\%$ thickness increase in early cycles) and relatively rapid capacity decay (5%–10% loss within tens of cycles). The localized clustering of Si promotes heterogeneous lithiation, mechanical cracking, and repetitive SEI reformation, leading to accelerated impedance growth. More integrated secondary-particle architectures, where Si is partially embedded in a carbonaceous or polymer-derived matrix, reduce structural heterogeneity and improve load distribution. At comparable mass loading, these materials generally show

moderate swelling and improved capacity retention ($>93\%$ in the first 50–100 cycles). The partial confinement of Si mitigates mechanical fracture, although incomplete homogeneity still allows stress concentration and nonuniform SEI evolution. The most stable performance is observed when Si is uniformly incorporated as nanoscale layers or domains within a Gr or carbon framework, often accompanied by built-in voids or compliant carbon shells.

Under the same practical electrode loading, these hierarchical or nanolayered designs lower swelling to lower than 50% and maintain capacities above 95% over long-term cycling. Their improved mechanical coupling and continuous conductive pathways suppress internal stress accumulation, limit SEI growth, and slow the rise of interfacial impedance. Collectively, these comparisons demonstrate that the degree of structural integration, rather than the absolute Si content, is the dominant factor controlling expansion suppression, impedance evolution, and cycle stability when electrodes are evaluated under comparable practical conditions. Table 5 compares the electrochemical performance of

TABLE 5 | Comparison of Si/Gr hybrid anodes with different structures.

Structure	Capacity (mAh g ⁻¹)	Performance	Mechanism	Refs.
Mixed SiO/Gr	400	76% @ 200th cycles	—	[229]
Mixed Si/Gr	450	85% @ 100th cycles	—	[230]
Mixed Si/Gr	500	rapid decay in the first 20 cycles	Reduced specific area, smaller expansion	[36]
Si-nanolayer-embedded Gr/C hybrids (SGC)	517	96% @ 100th cycles		
Mechanically blended n-Si/Gr	650	58.4% @ 50th @ 50 mA g ⁻¹	Interconnected	[231]
Gr/Si/graphene spherical hybrid	575	73.1% @ 50th @ 50 mA g ⁻¹	flake-Gr/Si network	
Ball milling mixed	655	78% @ 300th @ 0.2C	—	[232]
Core-shell Gr/Si-porous carbon hybrid	723	94.9% @ 100th	Core-shell buffering; reinforced conductive network	[233]
Fluidized-bed granulation (FBG) hybrid	600	>70% @ 400th	Improved conductivity; suppressed Si migration	[210]
Micro-nano structured Gr/ZnO-incorporated C-coated Si hybrid	1105	~90% @ 700th @ 600 mA g ⁻¹	Lower work function inhibits SEI growth; stable interfacial contact	[63]
Mixed Si/Gr	964	37% @100th @ 600 mA g ⁻¹		
Gr@Si-C	1100	54% @ 700th @ 600 mA g ⁻¹		
MF-processed 2D Gr-wrapped n-Si	1514	72.2% @ 100th @ 0.5C	2D framework suppresses fracture	[234]
Mixed SiO/Gr	1450	~50% @ 100th @ 0.5C	Rapid early decay; uneven Si distribution; continuous SEI growth	
Spray-dried, electrostatic self-assembly Gr/Si/GO/C hybrid	1212	81.7% @ 100th @ 200mAh g ⁻¹	Suppressed Si agglomeration; prevented structural collapse; limited Si-electrolyte reactions	[235]

different structures at similar specific capacities, arranged from lowest to highest, and provides an analysis of their respective advantages.

In summary, under similar specific capacities, the structure has a significant impact on performance, mainly in three aspects: the connection and maintenance of the conductive network, the contact with the electrolyte, and the resulting continuous growth of the SEI, and the stability of the mechanical structure. While the physical mixing mode is the simplest, its electrochemical performance is often unsatisfactory. Therefore, even when using a Si/Gr hybrid anode, the construction of an engineered structure should be considered.

3.4 | External Factors Affecting the Failure of Si/Gr Hybrid Anodes

In addition to the intrinsic degradation mechanisms of Si and the interaction effects within Si/Gr hybrids, the failure behavior of electrodes is also strongly modulated by external operating

conditions. Parameters such as temperature, cutoff potential, charge/discharge rate, external mechanical pressure, and electrode architecture have been systematically investigated, each revealing distinct pathways that accelerate or mitigate electrode degradation. Understanding these influences is essential for developing effective strategies to stabilize Si/Gr anodes in practical applications.

3.4.1 | Charge/Discharge Rate

Rate capability is one of the key factors driving the asymmetric degradation of Si and Gr. In general, at low rates (C/10), lithiation proceeds relatively uniformly. For example, Richter et al. quantitatively demonstrated that at 25% SOC [236], SiO_x reaches approximately 48% lithiation, whereas Gr is only 13% lithiated (Figure 13a). However, under fast-charging conditions (e.g., 3C), Gr experiences a larger potential drop than SiO_x, forcing a greater fraction of lithiation into the SiO_x phase and leading to a strongly inhomogeneous current distribution. Following fast charging, relaxation processes initiate

FIGURE 13 | (a) Illustration of the lithiation distribution when charging to 25 % SOC with different charge rates. Reproduced with permission [236]. Copyright 2024, Elsevier. (b) Electrochemical reaction distribution within the 60 μm thick Si/Gr anodes at different rates. Reproduced with permission [101]. Copyright 2024, Elsevier. (c) The stress distribution in Si/Gr hybrid anodes under different rates at 5% DOD for Gr and 100% DOD for Si. Reproduced with permission [237]. Copyright 2023, Elsevier. (d) The change in effective rates of Si and Gr during lithiation as a function of rates. Reproduced with permission [101]. Copyright 2024, Elsevier.

Li-ion exchange between SiO_x and Gr; however, the hysteric potential response of SiO_x prevents complete equilibration, resulting in persistent lithiation-state mismatches between the two components.

Real-time cell studies by Lu et al. further revealed that the effective lithiation rate of Si can reach up to 10C even when the applied C-rate is only 6C, whereas Gr lags significantly behind [101]. This imbalance results in severe polarization and

premature termination of the lithiation reaction, particularly under extreme fast charging conditions. Mechanically, charge-rate-dependent stress distributions also diverge between the two components (Figure 13b). At low C-rates, diffusion-induced stress in Si dominates due to steep Li concentration gradients, whereas at higher rates, Gr experiences greater stress, particularly at the electrode-separator interface during shallow depth of discharge (DOD), shifting toward the current collector at higher DOD (Figure 13c) [237].

Schweigart et al. observed that at high cycling rates, capacity fading originates almost exclusively from Si degradation, with Gr remaining structurally intact. Electrodes with high Si content (70 wt.%) suffer from complete amorphization and $\text{Li}_{15}\text{Si}_4$ formation, while those with lower Si fractions (30 wt.%) preserve residual crystalline domains and exhibit improved high-rate durability [196]. The current distribution between the two phases also differs significantly at different rates (Figure 13d). At low rates, the dominance of the current changes with the lithiation sequence, while at high rates, the interaction appears to be weakened, with Si always dominating.

3.4.2 | Cutoff Potential

The applied voltage window critically determines the degradation trajectory of Si/Gr hybrids. Cycling over a wide potential range (0.01–1.25 V) leads to significant capacity decay within the first cycles, while limiting lithiation to 0.65 V markedly mitigates capacity loss, resulting in smaller changes in particle morphology and lower porosity (Figure 14a). Deep delithiation protocols promote electrode swelling, impedance growth, and rapid capacity fading, whereas restricted cycling can improve the ICE in the initial cycles and sustain higher capacity retention [220].

Schweigart et al. demonstrated that cutoff voltages below 50 mV enable full Gr lithiation but simultaneously induce complete Si amorphization and $\text{Li}_{15}\text{Si}_4$ formation [196], both of which are highly detrimental to electrode stability (Figure 14b). By contrast, maintaining cutoff voltages ≥ 110 mV suppresses these failure modes, though at the expense of overall capacity. In practical testing, Si capacity loss can exceed 30% after only 5 kAh of throughput under moderate cycling, and reach up to 80% when operation is restricted to shallow SOC windows (0%–30%), suggesting that operational SOC management critically influences the practical utilization of Si in commercial cells [203].

3.4.3 | Temperature

Temperature strongly governs the kinetics of lithiation and delithiation, as well as the relative utilization of the Si and Gr components. This thermal effect significantly alters their phase-transition behavior. As revealed by operando XRD measurements led by Wu et al., under high-temperature storage, the Gr (002) diffraction peak of Gr/SiO_x electrodes shifted from the fully lithiated stage 1 (23.9°) to stage 2 (25.1°) within 4 h, whereas in pure Gr anodes, this transition required more than 10 h (Figure 14c) [100]. After 4 weeks of storage, the stage 1 peak completely disappeared in Gr/SiO_x electrodes, while it remained observable in Gr-only electrodes, confirming that SiO_x accelerates Li de-intercalation during calendar aging.

The schematic procedures illustrate a cascade of detrimental processes under HT storage (Figure 14d). It commences with the preferential degradation of SiO_x due to its unstable SEI, which lowers the electron energy level of SiO_x and creates a potential gradient relative to the passivated Gr. This gradient drives a spontaneous internal electron transfer from Gr to SiO_x, which,

in turn, forcibly delithiates the Gr. Consequently, the intrinsic instability of SiO_x propagates degradation to the otherwise stable Gr, leading to collective anode failure.

Similarly, Feinauer et al. demonstrated that the Si contribution to total capacity is strongly temperature-dependent: as temperature increased from 0°C to 55°C, Si lithiation capacity rose by 66%, whereas total capacity increased by only 16% [238]. This discrepancy highlights the different thermal sensitivities of the two components, with Si utilization being particularly temperature dependent. Although Si is expected to lithiate prior to Gr from a thermodynamic perspective, Richter et al. demonstrated that at lower temperatures (−20°C), kinetic factors in the form of activation barriers must be considered [239]. Under these conditions, Gr exhibits faster lithiation kinetics than Si, thereby being lithiated preferentially and deviating from the equilibrium behavior observed at room temperature.

3.4.4 | External Mechanical Compression

The application of external pressure significantly influences electrode aging, as it directly affects mechanical integrity, contact resistance, and stress evolution within the electrode structure. Müller et al. demonstrated that mild fixed compression (0.42 MPa) improved cycling stability by suppressing macroscopic swelling [240], but simultaneously generated highly nonuniform pressure distributions, with local hot spots exceeding 5 MPa near the current collector. By contrast, flexible compression limited the maximum local pressure to 3 MPa, resulting in more uniform stress distributions and reduced irreversible expansion after 70 cycles. These results suggest that tailored mechanical confinement can enhance electrode stability, though excessive rigidity may induce localized damage.

3.4.5 | Electrode Architecture and Composition

Electrode structural design exerts a decisive influence on degradation pathways. Conventional random Si/Gr mixtures often suffer from local stress accumulation and disordering of the Gr lattice during repeated cycling. Raman mapping of conventional Si/Gr blends after 100 cycles by Huang et al. [241] revealed a marked increase in the I_D/I_G , where the D band (~ 1350 cm^{−1}) corresponds to disordered carbon and the G band (~ 1580 cm^{−1}) represents the in-plane vibration of sp²-hybridized carbon atoms, indicative of severe disordering within Gr. The substantial (>300%) volume expansion of Si particles imposes interfacial stress that distorts Gr lattices and impedes Li-ion diffusion. In contrast, engineered layered Si/Gr electrodes preserved compact morphologies with significantly lower thickness expansion (195%) and exhibited no obvious cracking, demonstrating superior structural stability and electrochemical performance.

Taken together, the above analyses allow a more critical comparison of how compositional, structural, and operational factors jointly govern the cycling stability of Si/Gr hybrid anodes. First, Si content imposes the most fundamental constraint:

FIGURE 14 | (a) Morphologies of Si particles, obtained after cycling to different cutoff potentials. Reproduced with permission [220]. Copyright 2018, IOP Publishing. (b) Operando XRD and electrochemical data for Si/Gr anodes with different Si contents. Reproduced with permission [196]. Copyright 2024, Wiley. (c) In situ XRD of Gr full cell and SiO_x/Gr full cell during lithiation and subsequent HT storage. (d) Schematic procedures and relative energy diagrams. Reproduced with permission [100]. Copyright 2023, Springer Nature.

low-to-moderate Si loadings (~5–15 wt%) operate within a synergistic regime where Gr preserves electronic percolation and accommodates Si-induced strain, whereas higher Si fractions (≥ 20 –25 wt%) move the hybrid into an antagonistic regime characterized by amplified stress accumulation, accelerated SEI growth, and severe SOC heterogeneity, trends directly reflected in the particle fracture, interfacial disconnection, and Li-trapping

phenomena summarized above (Section 3.1). Electrode architecture modulates these intrinsic compositional effects by redistributing mechanical stress and ionic flux; engineered layered or graded structures generally suppress Gr lattice disordering and mitigate Si-driven microstructural collapse, whereas randomly mixed morphologies exacerbate current localization and structural instability.

FIGURE 15 | Summary of factors affecting the performance of Si/Gr hybrid anodes.

Beyond intrinsic design parameters, external operating conditions strongly reinforce or suppress these degradation pathways. High cycling rates drive asynchronous lithiation and steep Li concentration gradients, disproportionately accelerating degradation in Si-rich electrodes; deep cutoff voltages (<50 mV) trigger Si amorphization and $\text{Li}_{15}\text{Si}_4$ formation, while moderately elevated cutoff limits significantly alleviate these failure modes. Temperature and mechanical compression further tune the relative utilization and stress evolution of Si and Gr, often amplifying instability when Si remains the dominant contributor to capacity. Collectively, these comparative trends demonstrate that long-term stability arises only when Si content, electrode architecture, and operating protocols are co-optimized, and that deficiencies in any one of these dimensions, particularly at higher Si fractions, rapidly shift the system toward mechanically and electrochemically unstable degradation regimes.

Overall, the degradation of Si/C hybrid anodes is governed by both the intrinsic instability of Si (section 3.1) and the complex interactions between Si and Gr (section 3.2). These mechanisms are further influenced by external factors (section 3.3) such as temperature, cutoff potential, cycling rate, mechanical compression, and electrode design, summarized in Figure 15. A comprehensive understanding of these coupled effects is essential for developing durable Si/C anodes and provides the basis for discussing Si content and optimization strategies in the following section.

4 | Advanced Probing Strategies of Si/Gr Lithiation Dynamics

A well-recognized phenomenon in Si/Gr hybrid electrodes is the asynchronous and competitive (de)lithiation between Si and Gr.

A comprehensive understanding of this process is essential for accurately describing the lithiation state of each component and is therefore fundamental to the design and optimization of Si/Gr electrodes. However, directly analyzing such behaviors from macroscopic electrochemical data (e.g., current or voltage profiles) in half or full cells is challenging, as these quantities cannot explicitly distinguish the contributions of different active materials. The complexity of mesoscale architecture, the coexistence of multiple active materials, and the heterogeneous electrochemical environment further complicate the characterization of this competitive lithiation process [242].

4.1 | Advanced Characterizations

X-ray-based operando techniques, including synchrotron XRD and X-ray absorption spectroscopy, provide direct insights into lattice evolution, phase transitions, and local chemical environments during lithiation and delithiation (Figure 16a–f). The mold cell structure and test beamline setup have been extensively applied to pure Si and Gr electrodes [243–246], and are now increasingly employed in Si/Gr hybrids to probe the competitive lithiation and delithiation of the two components [247, 248]. For instance, EDXRD can directly monitor the lithiation state of Gr, while the corresponding lithiation state of Si was deduced from the overall electrode capacity.

Similarly, XRD spectral analyses can reveal the influence of active material working potentials on the competitive (de)lithiation behaviors within Si/Gr hybrids. Notably, these methodologies fundamentally rely on correlations between lattice parameters and lithiation states, which are difficult to rigorously validate, since additional factors such as mechanical stress may also influence lattice constants. Moreover, prolonged exposure to

Advanced characterizations for Si/Gr lithiation dynamics

FIGURE 16 | (a) Photograph of the microcell before an operando XRD experiment. (b) Cross-sectioned illustration of the microcell. Reproduced with permission [120]. Copyright 2019, American Chemical Society. (c) Schematic diagram of the investigated 18650-type cell, with the positioning of the incoming neutron beam (blue) and the diffracted neutrons (green). Reproduced with permission [239]. Copyright 2019, Wiley. (d) Scheme presenting the BM02 beamline setup at ESRF. Reproduced with permission [247]. Copyright 2019, American Chemical Society. (e) Operando cell for correlative SAXS/WAXS-CT performed in the hybrid anode at three positions. Reproduced with permission [199]. Copyright 2023, Wiley. (f) The reaction kinetics of the Si/Gr electrodes analyzed using side-view operando observation. Reproduced with permission [105]. Copyright 2023, Elsevier.

high-energy radiation may alter crystal structures, inducing effects ranging from subtle lattice distortions to artificial phase transitions, and often requires large-scale synchrotron facilities.

Microscopic characterization techniques, including in situ transmission electron microscopy (TEM) [249–251], scanning electron microscopy (SEM) [252, 253], and advanced optical microscopy [254, 255], enable direct visualization of morphological evolution, fracture behavior, and interfacial reactions in Si/Gr systems. These techniques reveal spatial heterogeneity of lithiation, crack propagation, and carbon buffering effects with high temporal and spatial resolution. For example, Lee et al. utilized side-view operando optical microscopy to study the charge heterogeneity in Si/Gr electrodes [105]. Their findings revealed that during lithiation, Si mitigates the depth heterogeneity of Gr due to its rapid surface diffusion and kinetic overpotential, whereas delithiation is dominated by the electrochemical potential difference, leading to sequential reactions from Gr to Si. These insights provide critical guidance for the rational design of high-energy-density Si/Gr electrodes. They provide intuitive, real-space images at the nanoscale, but their application can be hindered by beam-induced damage and the limited representativeness of model electrodes.

Operando Raman spectroscopy is a widely used technique for monitoring bonding states, degree of disorder, and structural evolution in both Si and carbonaceous domains. This method provides insights into the role of graphitic or amorphous carbon in stress accommodation and conductivity retention [256–259]. It is particularly effective for distinguishing lithiation-induced amorphization of Si and the evolution of carbon D/G bands. Ruther et al. used Raman microspectroscopy combined with mapping and reported that the hybrid anodes are not homogeneous but segregate into Gr-rich and Si-rich phases [96]. Lithiation does not proceed uniformly either. It is non-destructive and highly sensitive to bonding environments, yet suffers from shallow penetration depth and interference from fluorescence signals.

Solid-state and operando NMR techniques provide unique insights into Li-ion dynamics, local environments, and Li distribution in heterogeneous hybrid electrodes. NMR is particularly useful for disentangling Li storage contributions from Si [260], Gr [261–263], and interfacial phases, enabling a quantitative understanding of heterogeneous lithiation. For example, Park et al. analyzed NMR spectra of electrodes at various states of discharge (SOD) and found that, at the onset of discharge, the lithiation degree of LiSi_y exceeds that of LiC_x [264]. The two values intersect before reaching 50% SOD, indicating a dynamic shift in the dominant lithiation host as cycling progresses.

In addition to these mainstream methods, neutron depth profiling provides unique sensitivity to Li distribution [265]. For example, Graae et al. conducted a comprehensive comparison of the phase transition behaviors of Si and Gr using neutron diffraction and synchrotron X-ray diffraction [104], while Möller et al. employed MeV Ion Beam Analysis to investigate lithiation depth and lateral profiles in Si-containing Gr electrodes [266]. These approaches add valuable perspectives but are often limited by instrumental complexity and experimental constraints.

4.2 | Simulation and Modeling Approaches

While in situ experimental techniques provide valuable insights into the competitive (de)lithiation dynamics of Si/Gr electrodes, they are often limited by high technical costs and feasibility constraints. Computational modeling has therefore emerged as a powerful complementary approach to probe the fundamental structure–performance relationships of electrodes and battery systems.

At the atomic scale, first-principles calculations and ab initio molecular dynamics (AIMD) simulations have proven indispensable for understanding the thermodynamics, bonding environments, and charge transfer mechanisms at atomic interfaces [267–271]. For example, Feng et al. demonstrated through AIMD that the irreversible capacity loss in Si/Gr hybrids originates from shortened Li–Si and Li–C bond lengths at the interface [272]. Similarly, systematic investigations of bulk, surface, and interfacial phases of Si/Gr hybrids have revealed that interfacial stability is strongly dependent on the lithiation state of Li_xSi domains (Figure 17a,b) [273]. Surface defects in the carbon matrix accelerate electrolyte decomposition and SEI formation [274], while the formation of Si/C interfaces is generally endothermic and metastable unless driven by external electrochemical or thermal energy. These atomistic insights provide critical parameters for higher-scale modeling, such as interfacial energies, reaction barriers, and effective transport properties.

Building upon atomic-scale descriptions, mesoscale electrochemical models extend the analysis to particle-level kinetics, diffusion, and stress evolution. Classical porous electrode theory and the pseudo-2D (P2D) model, first introduced by Newman and Doyle, have been widely adapted to study LIBs [275, 276]. Early approaches often treated Si/Gr hybrids as a single homogenized material with averaged open-circuit potentials and effective transport parameters, which allowed reproduction of bulk voltage–capacity profiles but overlooked the intrinsic differences between Si and Gr.

To address this limitation, advanced multiparticle models have been proposed. Jiang et al. introduced a kinetic decomposition framework that treats Si and Gr as independent particle populations [277], and further defined a dimensionless competition factor (χ) to quantify current partitioning between the two components. This framework not only rationalizes voltage hysteresis and plateau shifts but also provides guidance for cycling protocol design to mitigate electrode degradation. Similarly, Gao et al. developed a coupled electrochemical–mechanical model explicitly resolving Si oxide and Gr phases [278], showing how heterogeneous stress and diffusion fields give rise to lithiation heterogeneity. Lory et al. proposed a P2D model that incorporates Gr, a carbon matrix, and n-Si embedded within the matrix [279], following Li concentrations in each of the three active phases. This model captures competitive lithiation among the phases and reproduces the rate-dependent reaction pathways observed experimentally.

Mechanical effects play a central role in the degradation of Si/Gr anodes, and several models have introduced explicit electrochemical–mechanical coupling. Frameworks like

FIGURE 17 | (a) Heterogeneous Li_xSi - Li_yC systems including variously orientated interfaces. (b) interfacial tensions in heterogeneous Li_xSi - Li_yC systems as a function of their Li content. Reproduced with permission [273]. Copyright 2022, Royal Society of Chemistry. (c) Degradation sub-model interaction in the PyBaMM framework. Reproduced with permission [280]. Copyright 2024, Elsevier. (d) Calculated SIO of Si as a function of Si SOL and direction of reaction. Reproduced with permission [281]. Copyright 2025, Elsevier. (e) Schematic drawing of finite volume discretization of porous electrodes across their thickness. Reproduced with permission [107]. Copyright 2023, IOP Publishing. (f) Workflow diagram of modeling. Reproduced with permission [106]. Copyright 2021, Elsevier.

representative volume element (RVE) simulations can demonstrate that preferential lithiation, which is driven by equilibrium potential differences and kinetic asymmetries, leads to markedly different strain and porosity evolutions compared to homogenized assumptions. Additionally, PyBaMM integrates P2D electrochemical models with degradation physics, enabling quantitative predictions of dynamic capacity loss in Si/Gr systems (Figure 17c) [280].

In a notable contribution, a thermodynamically consistent coupling between stress and electrochemistry has been

formulated (Figure 17d) [281], in which hydrostatic and biaxial stresses are converted into stress-induced overpotentials that shift the equilibrium potential in Butler–Volmer kinetics. This approach successfully reproduces history-dependent lithiation/delithiation hysteresis and provides a physical explanation for direction-dependent polarization and additional heat generation during cycling. Additional refinements, such as the introduction of memory variables to capture path-dependent voltage hysteresis and the incorporation of electrode-thickness effects, further enhance predictive accuracy [282]. These modeling frameworks have been increasingly

implemented in open-source simulation platforms (Figure 17e) [107].

Another rapidly developing direction is the integration of realistic 3D electrode structures into electrochemical simulations. Microstructure-resolved models can be constructed using random particle packing, physics-based simulations such as coarse-grained molecular dynamics (CGMD) or discrete element methods (DEM), and data-driven generative approaches. Liu et al. employed CGMD to develop a time-resolved 3D model of Gr/Si hybrid electrodes [106], resolving the spatial distribution of Si particles and validating fundamental interaction mechanisms. Their simulations confirmed Li crosstalk between Gr and Si (Figure 17f), localized Si degradation due to potential mismatches, and mass-transport limitations that contribute to uneven lithiation.

Electrode- and cell-level models now incorporate degradation phenomena such as SEI growth, loss of active material (LAM), and coupling with different cathodes [283, 284]. The P2D model integrating SEI growth and LAM modules can explain differences between fresh and aged battery performance. Such combined experimental-modeling approaches underscore the unique complexity of hybrid anodes and provide essential tools for diagnosing and mitigating degradation.

4.3 | Equivalent and Model Experimental Configurations for Si/Gr Anodes

Electrochemical analyses in full-cell configurations, where Si/Gr anodes are paired with different cathodes, provide further insights into the competitive (de)lithiation behaviors of hybrid electrodes [285]. For instance, the group of Matilda Klett introduced an external Li-metal reference electrode (RE) for potential measurements and an internal Li_xSn RE for impedance monitoring in NCM523||Si/Gr cells [286]. This setup enabled detailed tracking of capacity loss, SOC shifts, active material utilization, and impedance evolution in Li-limited full cells. Similarly, Zhang et al. employed a full-cell configuration (NMC622||Si/Gr) and applied the differential potential analysis approach [287], in combination with voltage profiles obtained from a three-electrode setup, to deconvolute overlapping capacity contributions. This approach enabled the separation of Si-NMC and Gr-NMC capacities, thereby confirming that the electrochemical capacity associated with Si-NMC undergoes rapid fading.

Schmitt et al. reported pronounced changes in the OCP profile of Si-Gr half-cells during the cycle aging of full cells [288]. Their differential voltage (DV) analyses confirmed the preferential degradation of Si compared to Gr. Kim et al. developed a simplified real-time analysis system by constructing a reaction distribution analysis (RDA) cell (Figure 18a) [101], in which Si and Gr electrodes are electrically short-circuited through direct contact or conductive carbon. Heubner et al. further proposed a refined experimental method by designing parallel Si and Gr electrodes connected within a model hybrid cell (Figure 18b) [202]. This configuration enabled direct measurement of the individual current response of each component, as well as separation of their respective dQ/dV curves.

The above-mentioned approach allowed the clear identification of formation-cycle dynamics, rate-dependent reaction distributions, and the contribution of each component to overall capacity during pulse loading and relaxation. From a thermodynamic perspective, the hybrid electrode can be regarded as two independent electrodes connected by a low-resistance link. The applied current is thereby partitioned between Si and Gr according to their respective reaction kinetics, enabling precise resolution of their dynamic behaviors under different charge/discharge conditions.

In addition, several equivalent operando characterization strategies have been developed. Li et al. developed a cantilever-based curvature measurement system (Figure 18c) to correlate electrode bending with the lithiation/delithiation states of Si/Gr electrodes [102]. During charging, both Si and Gr expand due to lithiation, causing measurable electrode bending, whereas during discharging, the bending gradually relaxes. By mapping curvature evolution to electrode capacity, this method provides a scalable and straightforward means to probe competitive (de)lithiation dynamics without requiring crystalline materials or distinct phase transitions.

Beyond operando measurements, equivalent approaches at the materials level have also elucidated the intrinsic competition between active components. Frankenstein et al. employed operando XRD to identify “transfer lithiation” [289], in which Li initially stored in Gr migrates to Si within the hybrid electrode (Figure 18d). Their results revealed accelerated consumption of LiC_6 in thinner Si/Gr hybrids, indicative of faster transfer lithiation kinetics. Complementary solid-state ^7Li NMR experiments further confirmed this process by directly monitoring the redistribution of Li between pre-lithiated Gr and Si powders.

Collectively, these equivalent experimental designs, ranging from reference electrode integration and parallel-cell architectures to operando curvature and NMR/XRD analyses, provide essential methodologies to disentangle the complex, competitive (de)lithiation processes in Si/Gr hybrid anodes. Different research methods have their own advantages and disadvantages. In order to accurately interpret the complex electrochemical behavior of the hybrid negative electrode and the resulting degradation behavior of the active material failure battery, a combination of multiple methods is required.

5 | Electrolyte Engineering of Si/Gr Hybrid Anode

The electrolyte plays a decisive role in the electrochemical behavior and long-term stability of Si/Gr anodes, because Si and Gr exhibit intrinsically different interfacial reaction pathways in liquid electrolytes. While Gr forms a thin and stable SEI in conventional $\text{LiPF}_6\text{-EC/EMC}$ carbonate electrolytes, Si undergoes severe SEI fracture and regeneration due to its large volume change, resulting in rapid electrolyte consumption and low ICE. These contrasting behaviors set the boundary conditions for Si/C hybrids: the electrolyte must simultaneously satisfy the “Gr-friendly” requirement for low parasitic reactions and thin SEI formation and the “Si-friendly” requirement for LiF-rich, mechanically robust SEIs. As a result, electrolyte engineering

FIGURE 18 | (a) Schematic of the reaction dynamics analysis cell and analysis system. Reproduced with permission [101]. Copyright 2024, Elsevier. (b) Schematic representation of MLBE. Reproduced with permission [202]. Copyright 2022, Wiley. (c) Schematic diagram of the assembled model battery. Reproduced with permission [102]. Copyright 2025, Wiley. (d) Schematic illustration of the transfer-lithiation process using 7Li NMR experiments. Reproduced with permission [289]. Copyright 2025, Wiley.

becomes indispensable for achieving balanced lithiation behavior and stable cycling in Si/C electrodes.

In carbonate systems, fluoroethylene carbonate (FEC) is widely recognized as an essential additive for stabilizing Si. Its preferential reduction produces a LiF-rich SEI that improves interfacial mechanical integrity and enhances the ICE [290–293]. However, recent studies have shown that in Si/C hybrid anodes, FEC is consumed rapidly through sequential reduction on both Si and Gr surfaces, leading to the formation of VC, LiF, and deeper decomposition products. This accelerated consumption causes effective FEC concentration to diminish early in cycling and necessitates careful control of its dosage. Excessive FEC, typically above about 20 wt%, can also induce undesirable reactions on Gr, including excessive SEI growth and gas evolution, which increase impedance and degrade long-term performance [294, 295]. Therefore, moderate FEC contents, generally in the range of 5–15 wt%, are considered optimal for balancing Si stabilization with Gr compatibility.

Vinylene carbonate (VC), often added at low levels, provides complementary benefits by improving SEI elasticity and mitigating late-stage SEI thickening, but excessive VC can similarly increase impedance at Gr interfaces [296]. Consequently, VC is typically used as a secondary additive in small proportions to reinforce overall SEI stability.

The broader optimization of electrolytes for Si/C hybrid anodes involves simultaneous tuning of Li salts, solvent mixtures, and multi-component additive packages. LiPF₆ remains the most widely used salt due to its compatibility with Gr and its established performance in commercial systems, though its limited chemical stability and HF formation present challenges for Si-rich interfaces. LiFSI, by contrast, promotes the formation of LiF-enriched SEIs favorable for Si but can induce corrosion on aluminum current collectors [297] and trigger unwanted reactions on Gr [298]. Hybrid salt systems that combine LiPF₆ and LiFSI have therefore been proposed as a balanced approach to improve Si interfacial stability without compromising Gr performance.

Considering sustainability and ease of recycling, fluorine-free electrolytes are another key focus, with Li bis(oxalate)borate (LiBOB) being the most extensively studied fluorine-free salt. LiBOB exhibits good electrochemical performance on Gr electrodes, and thin-film Si electrodes show even better capacity retention when using LiBOB-based electrolytes. However, the results are not entirely positive in mixed anodes; the behavior of LiBOB-based electrolytes differs when Si and Gr are combined, with a preferential salt decomposition observed over Gr particles compared to Si [299]. EDX elemental mapping analysis indicates that the boron species concentration is higher on Gr than in Si regions. (Figure 19a). This suggests that the LiBOB-based

Electrolyte system for Si/Gr anodes

FIGURE 19 | (a) EDX mapping of the Si/Gr electrodes after five cycles. Reproduced with permission [299]. Copyright 2024, IOP Publishing. (b) Si 2p and C 1s spectra of SEI formed in electrolytes, and a structure illustration of the SEI. Reproduced with permission [300]. Copyright 2023, Wiley. (c) Electrochemical transformations of DMVC derivatives and design of a deformable and stable SEI. Reproduced with permission [301]. Copyright 2021, Springer Nature. (d) Schematic illustration of the synergistic function of VC and LiDFP. Reproduced with permission [302]. Copyright 2023, American Chemical Society. (e) The von Mises stress distribution between the Si and Cu current collectors and differential charge diagrams. Reproduced with permission [303]. Copyright 2024, Elsevier. (f) Schematic of solvent-induced selective dissolution for SEI. Reproduced with permission [304]. Copyright 2023, Springer Nature. (g) Schematic of surface and bulk stabilization of Si anodes with mixed-multivalent additives. Reproduced with permission [305]. Copyright 2024, American Chemical Society.

electrolyte forms a less effective SEI on Si particles when Gr is also present in the electrode.

Despite the demanding interface of Si requirements, EC-based carbonate solvents such as EC-EMC or EC-DMC remain mainstream choices because they offer high conductivity, practical viscosity, and robust passivation of Gr. Adjusting the EC/EMC ratio, often by reducing EC content to suppress gas evolution, while compensating with moderate amounts of FEC, is a common and effective formulation strategy. In the 1,2-dimethoxyethane (DME) system, to construct a robust SEI suitable for Si-based anodes, featuring an inorganic-rich inner layer and a highly polymerized outer layer, the solvation properties and reductive polymerization behavior of the resulting cyclic ether (tetrahydrofuran, THF) are significantly different from those of DME by simultaneously reducing the etheroxy groups in DME and increasing its molecular unsaturation.

Unlike LHCE-DME electrolytes, LHCE-THF electrolytes have a weaker solvation structure, allowing more anions to coordinate with Li ion in the first sheath layer, thus achieving rapid desolvation kinetics and forming an inorganic-rich SEI [300]. Simultaneously, the unsaturated cyclic structure of the THF solvent forms a tough and elastic SEI that can adapt well to volume changes in the Si anode and remain stable during long-term cycling. (Figure 19b). Alongside FEC and VC, more functional additives and the synergistic effect of multiple additives jointly contribute to the use of Si-C hybrid anodes.

Park et al. [301] synthesized functional VC derivatives with $-\text{OCF}_3$ and trimethylsiloxy ($-\text{OTMS}$) groups as additives (Figure 19c). The $-\text{OCF}_3$ group on dimethyl vinylene carbonate (DMVC) can serve as an effective free radical precursor through single-electron reduction, thereby achieving continuous chain growth steps; the OTMS group in DMVC-OTMS can effectively remove HF that severely damages the CEI and SEIs, thereby maintaining the structural integrity of the CEI and SEIs. Song et al. [302] utilized the synergistic effect of VC and LiDFP additives to construct an effective SEI with good flexibility and high ionic conductivity, thereby significantly improving the cycle stability and rate stability of Si@C anodes (Figure 19d).

Pan et al. [303] used a Si-containing macromolecular electrolyte additive, vinyl-terminated polydimethylsiloxane (Vi-PDMS), to improve cycle stability. The $\text{C}=\text{C}$ bonds in Vi-PDMS react with electrolyte byproducts (HF), thereby suppressing side reactions between HF and the solvent. Furthermore, the Si-containing macromolecular Li salt generated after Vi-PDMS decomposition serves as part of the SEI, ensuring high ionic conductivity and improving adhesion between the current collector and Si (Figure 19e). This alleviates stress concentration at the interface between Si particles and the copper current collector caused by expansion forces.

Tian et al. [304] proposed a solvent-induced selective dissolution strategy, as shown in Figure 19f, introducing a high-donor-number solvent, γ -butyrolactone, into conventional electrolytes. This selectively dissolves low-modulus components in the SEI, such as alkyl Li carbonate, thus retaining a stable SEI mainly composed of Li fluoride and polycarbonate during cycling. Besides Li salts, when using a mixture of calcium and magnesium

multivalent cations as electrolyte additives (Figure 19g), calcium and magnesium ions in the electrolyte can form a relatively thermodynamically stable quaternary Li-Ca-Mg-Si Zintl phase in situ, resulting in a more stable and denser SEI on the Si particle surface. [305] Table 6 lists the battery performance of different electrolyte systems (from conventional electrolytes to functional additives) based on Si/Gr hybrid anodes.

In summary, electrolyte formulation is central to the viability of Si/C hybrid anodes, as it must navigate the conflicting interfacial requirements of Si and Gr within a shared electrode architecture. At room temperature, optimized carbonate electrolytes employing balanced combinations of $\text{LiPF}_6/\text{LiFSI}$ salts, adjusted EC-(EMC/DMC) solvent ratios, and carefully controlled additive packages, especially moderate FEC with low VC content, represent the most effective and practical approach. Current research continues to advance toward integrated electrolyte design in which salts, solvents, and additives are co-engineered to achieve stable SEI chemistry, suppress parasitic reactions, and fully leverage the potential of Si/C hybrid anodes.

6 | Possible Optimization Tactics on the Match Performance

With the emergence of Si/Gr hybrid anodes in next-generation LIBs, various strategies have been developed to address the intrinsic mismatch between the two active materials. These can be broadly divided into material-level modifications and electrode-level configurations, both of which are essential to improve electrochemical stability and practical performance.

6.1 | Material-Level Strategies

At the material level, regulation of lithiation dynamics plays a critical role. Since mixing Si with Gr can introduce certain adverse interactions, an alternative approach is to replace Gr with other carbon components. Sun et al. revealed that employing carbon with different degrees of graphitization as the carbon component in Si/C hybrid anodes can regulate the heterogeneous lithiation sequence [205], mitigate bidirectional Li diffusion during the biphasic lithiation stage, and thereby enhance long-term cycling stability.

Doping and structural modulation of the Si component also appear to be effective strategies for tuning its lithiation sequence. Tao et al. first proposed that the competitive co-lithiation behavior in Si/Gr anodes is governed by interfacial polarization in Si [313], which determines preferential Li deposition sites and SEI formation. By tuning Li-ion diffusion kinetics in Si, the electrochemical potential can be balanced, thereby alleviating the lithiation mismatch between Si and Gr (Figure 20a). Since mixing Si with Gr can introduce certain adverse interactions, an alternative approach is to replace Gr with other carbon components.

Interface engineering is another key approach to improve compatibility between Si and Gr (Figure 20b-e). Li et al. obtained Si/Gr hybrids with excellent conductivity and Li-ion transport ability by introducing hydroxyl and amino groups on

FIGURE 20 | (a) XRD patterns at different lithiation states and schematic diagram of the lithiation process. Reproduced with permission [313]. Copyright 2023, Elsevier. (b) Schematic diagram of the preparation of Si/Gr materials. Reproduced with permission [314]. Copyright 2024, Elsevier. (c) Process flow of Si@Gr hybrid preparation consisting of grinding, fluidized bed granulation, subsequent pitch coating, and carbonization. Reproduced with permission [210]. Copyright 2021, Elsevier. (d) Schematic illustration of the Gr@Si@C anode and MF process for Gr@Si@C hybrid fabrication. Reproduced with permission [234]. Copyright 2025, Wiley. (e) Schematic illustration of the synthesis process Si/C materials. Reproduced with permission [315]. Copyright 2025, Elsevier. (f) Electrochemical performance of Si@GAC@Gr materials. Reproduced with permission [316]. Copyright 2022, Elsevier. (g) Anode profiles. Reproduced with permission [317]. Copyright 2020, IOP Publishing. (h) Cycle number at 80% of the maximum capacity. Reproduced with permission [318]. Copyright 2019, IOP Publishing.

TABLE 6 | Cell performances of Si-based electrodes in representative electrolyte systems.

Electrode	Electrolyte	Cell	Performance	Refs.
n-Si/C	1 M LiPF ₆ in EC/DMC (1/1) +10%VC	Li In-Si/C	80% @ 250 mA g ⁻¹ @ 100th	[306]
Si/Gr	0.5 M LiPF ₆ + 0.5 M LiFSI in EC/DEC (3/7) 15% FEC	LiCoO ₂ Si/C	92.9% @ 1C @ 500th	[307]
Si/C + Gr	LiTFSI-DME/HFE	NCM811 Si/C	83.9% @ 100 mA g ⁻¹ @ 1000th	[308]
Si@Graphene	1 M LiPF ₆ in EC/DEC/DMC+ 1% IEM + 9% FEC	Li Si/G	1300 mAh g ⁻¹ @ 1 A g ⁻¹ @ 100th	[309]
Si/C	1.2 M LiFSI/0.05 M LiDFOB in DME/HFE/FEC	Li Si/C	87.6% @ 0.2C @ 150th	[28]
Si/Gr	1.2 M LiFSI in TEP/FEC/BTFE (1.2/0.13/4) +1.2% FEC	Li Si/Gr	73.4% @ 0.75 mA cm ⁻² @ 300th	[310]
Si/Gr	1 M LiPF ₆ in EC/DEC + 2% TMSPI	NMC333 Si/Gr	>90% @ 0.5C @ 600th	
SNG+Gr	1.15 M LiPF ₆ in EC/EMC (3/7) + 5% FEC+0.5%VC+0.5%DMVC-OCF3+0.5%DMVC-OTMS	NMC811 Si/Gr	80% @ 0.5C @ 50th	[311]
Si/Gr	1 M LiTFSI in THF+TTE	NCM811 Si/C	81.5% @ 1C @ 400th	[301]
SiO/Gr	1 M LiFSI in FEC+BFEC	LiFePO ₄ Si/Gr	80% @ 0.5C @ 600th	[300]
		NMC811 SiO/Gr	92% @ 0.5C @ 100th	[312]

Si surfaces, followed by asphalt coating and alkaline etching [314]. The homogeneous dispersion significantly suppressed particle fracture and volume-induced capacity fading. Muller et al. extended this concept through a scalable fluidized bed granulation method combined with carbon coating, producing Si@Gr/C hybrids that achieved capacities over 600 mAh g⁻¹ [210], nearly double that of Gr. Kim et al. [234] further synthesized Gr@Si@C microspherical hybrids via mechanofusion, which delivered high volumetric energy density and robust cycling performance. Similarly, the use of biogum-derived carbon precursors such as gum arabic, guar gum, and xanthan gum enabled the preparation of Si@C hybrids. When combined with artificial Gr (Figure 20f), these multiphase structures shortened electron pathways and enhanced rate capability while maintaining a high ICE [315, 316].

Pre-lithiation provides an additional avenue to counteract the initial irreversible capacity loss and improve the lithiation balance between Si and Gr. Rodrigues et al. reported that highly pre-lithiated Si/Gr electrodes form Li-deficient Li_xSi phases acting as Li reservoirs (Figure 20g) [317], which stabilize cycling performance. Jantke et al. further demonstrated that partial pre-lithiation of micron-sized Si particles (25%–35% lithiation) enables stable cycling over 200 cycles with ICE values approaching 95% (Figure 20g) [318]. This strategy improved volumetric capacity by ~40% compared to Gr-based electrodes, as shown in Figure 20g,h, while highlighting that the optimal pre-lithiation degree strongly depends on the intended application.

6.2 | Electrode-Level Strategies

Beyond material design, electrode architecture and configuration play a decisive role in determining the electrochemical

stability of Si/Gr hybrids. This dictates the spatial distribution of reaction sites, mechanical stress accommodation, and interfacial stability, thereby controlling long-term degradation behavior. Zhang et al. developed functionally graded electrodes with a parabolic Si distribution through the thickness [319], which alleviated stress accumulation, prevented electrode cracking, and shortened Li-ion transport pathways. These graded designs achieved both high capacity and long-term cycling stability, as shown in Figure 21a. Similarly, layered electrodes significantly affect SEI behavior: in Si-on-top designs, unconstrained Si expansion causes excessive SEI growth, while Gr-on-top electrodes mechanically restrict Si swelling, leading to thinner and more stable SEIs with improved cycling life (Figure 21b,c) [241].

Porosity engineering has also emerged as a practical solution to buffer volume expansion. Yoo et al. proposed a bilayer Si/Gr electrode with a porous Si-rich upper layer and a dense Gr-rich lower layer [320]. The upper layer absorbed Si expansion, while the lower layer enhanced adhesion to the Cu current collector and suppressed delamination. Even at high Si content (30 wt%), this configuration maintained considerable capacity and remarkable stability, underscoring the industrial potential of porosity gradient designs (Figure 21d,e).

Another important factor is electrolyte wettability, because it directly influences ionic transport, SEI formation, and overall interfacial stability within the electrode. Kim et al. introduced an electrochemical diagnostic indicator based on DV analysis to monitor electrode wetting [321]. Insufficient or heterogeneous wetting caused localized overpotentials and characteristic Si-related features in DV profiles, as shown in Figure 21f,g. This diagnostic method allows wetting states to be monitored during manufacturing, ensuring uniform ionic transport and improving overall cycling stability.

FIGURE 21 | (a) Schematic illustration of the Si/Gr electrodes with chemo-mechanical simulated out-of-plane deflections. (b) Schematic illustration of the manufacturing process of Si/Gr electrodes. Reproduced with permission [319]. Copyright 2022, American Chemical Society. (c) Failure mechanism of the conventional and layered Si/Gr electrodes. Reproduced with permission [241]. Copyright 2025, Elsevier. (d) B bilayer electrode fabrication process and working mechanism. Reproduced with permission [320]. Copyright 2024, Wiley. (e, f) The DV profiles (e) and the capacity ratios of Si (f) in the cylindrical cells with different contents of electrolyte at various rates. (g) Correlation of deg-SC@EOC with the Si capacity ratios and the cell overpotential. Reproduced with permission [321]. Copyright 2025, Elsevier.

In conclusion, optimization strategies for Si/C hybrid anodes require coordinated progress at both the material and electrode levels. Material-level strategies should be integrated with engineering-oriented approaches at the electrode or cell level [322]. Together, these strategies provide a comprehensive framework to overcome the intrinsic mismatch between Si and Gr, advancing the development of high-performance and durable Si/C hybrid anodes.

7 | Full-Cell Considerations and Practical Implementation of Si/Gr Anodes

Si-containing Gr anodes have already been introduced in high-end consumer electronics and are entering electric-vehicle cells, but the Si fraction in current large-volume commercial LIBs remains relatively low. Recent analyses indicate that most commercial Si-based anodes incorporate Si in the form of micron-sized SiO_x blended with Gr, with typical Si (or SiO_x) contents below ~ 10 wt% in the anode active material. This trend is consistent with industrial surveys reported in the literature, which show that SiO_x/Gr hybrids used in commercial cells generally deliver reversible capacities in the range of 450–650 mAh g^{-1} . Major suppliers have introduced SiO_x/Gr or Si/C hybrid products that are widely deployed in consumer-electronics batteries, confirming that low-Si SiO_x/Gr hybrids remain the dominant industrial pathway.

7.1 | Commercial Si/Gr Systems

Some reports note that higher-Si commercial solutions are beginning to appear in the EV sector. Si-rich hybrid anodes, enabled by engineered Si/C architectures and interface design, can provide significant cell-level energy-density improvements. A novel micron-sized Si/C hybrid particle, pioneered by Sila Nanotechnologies, has garnered widespread attention in industry. In 2022, Group14 Technologies (G14) achieved a significant breakthrough in full-cell performance with its Si/C anode, which has been validated by several leading manufacturers, making it one of the most promising solutions for Si-based anodes in high-energy-density LIBs [323]. Despite the significant progress made, whether these materials can become the ultimate solution for Si-based anodes remains to be seen.

Taken together, these recent literature reports underscore that, although low-Si Si/Gr hybrids currently dominate practical applications, the complex and heterogeneous electrochemical interactions between Si and Gr remain insufficiently resolved. A more detailed understanding of these coupled behaviors is still essential for addressing the performance limitations observed under practical operating conditions and for enabling broader deployment of Si/Gr hybrid anodes.

7.2 | Full-Cell Considerations and Practical Parameters

Full-cell investigations provide a more nuanced picture of how Si/Gr hybrid anodes behave under realistic operating constraints, revealing that the degree of heterogeneity is strongly dependent

on both the Si fraction and the applied N/P ratio. Studies that systematically vary Si content consistently show that even small increases in Si loading introduce disproportionately large changes in swelling behavior, ICE, and impedance evolution. We then briefly discussed the impact of practical parameters applied to full cells, including electrode porosity, binder, NP ratio, pre-lithiation strategy, etc., on the ICE and swelling behavior of the battery.

In the Si/Gr hybrid anode, the ICE is significantly affected by the large amount of irreversible Li consumption during the formation of SEI on Si and Gr and the mismatch of lithiation potential between Si and Gr. The large specific surface area and dynamic volume change of Si will continuously expose new surfaces, resulting in significant Li loss in the first cycle. Obviously, the added Si content intrinsically determines the degree of ICE decline. In addition, considering the Si dioxide layer on the surface of Si-based materials, three reactions will occur during the diffusion of Li into the Si/Gr material: (i) Li ions migrate into the electrolyte to form irreversible organic Li compounds; (ii) Li reaches the Si surface and reacts with SiO_2 to form an irreversible phase; (iii) the remaining Li is embedded in Si and Gr [324]. Therefore, Liu's work [325] shows that the ICE of the Si/Gr anode material is not only affected by the specific surface area, but also by the ion and charge transfer impedance and the phase interface. The above three factors will affect the reaction kinetics and the reversible/irreversible phase content ratio of the Si/Gr material and ultimately affect the ICE of the Si/G hybrid material. From a full-cell perspective, the irreversible Li consumption associated with Si/Gr inevitably depletes the limited lithium inventory supplied by the cathode, making the ICE loss more detrimental than in half-cell systems. This lithium imbalance further accelerates capacity decay during cycling, underscoring the necessity of improving the ICE of Si/Gr hybrid anodes for practical full-cell applications. The optimization strategies mentioned in the article are also a way to improve ICE.

The N/P ratio further modulates these heterogeneities by altering the accessible Li inventory and the extent to which Si is allowed to lithiate. Moderate N/P ratios (1.05–1.15) generally produce more homogeneous lithiation profiles across Si/Gr hybrids by preventing deep lithiation of Si and suppressing excessive mechanical strain. However, lower N/P ratios (≈ 1.0 or below) narrow the Li buffer of the cathode and shift the anode toward deeper and more spatially uneven Si utilization, often leading to sharp local overpotentials, accelerated SEI formation, and nonuniform current distribution. Conversely, overbalancing the anode (N/P > 1.3–1.5) mitigates Li plating but results in under-utilized Si domains that gradually become inactive due to insufficient cycling of the surrounding Gr matrix [326]. These coupled effects, composition-driven swelling, N/P-regulated lithiation depth, and evolving mechanical–electrochemical feedback, explain why full-cell performance often diverges substantially from half-cell predictions and why Si/Gr hybrids with nominally similar capacities can exhibit markedly different aging behaviors.

The densification level critically influences both mechanical stability and electrochemical performance because Si and Gr exhibit distinct packing behaviors and expansion characteristics. Higher compaction improves volumetric energy density and particle–particle contact; however, excessive densification

compresses pore channels, limits electrolyte wetting, and intensifies mechanical constraints on Si, thereby exacerbating stress heterogeneity and promoting microcracking or loss of electrical contact. Another parameter strongly correlated with densification is porosity.

Porosity of the anodes with relevant loadings is one of the critical parameters directly related to the ability of Li ions to reversibly reach active materials within the whole thickness of the electrode under the conditions of the test, including high C-rate operation [327]. Failure analysis of 18650 batteries with negative electrode (Si/Gr-500mAh g⁻¹) porosities of 30% and 40% after formation and cycling showed that the battery with a negative electrode porosity of 30% had a 9% higher capacity after formation than the battery with 40% porosity, but its cycle performance was worse. For the battery with an anode porosity of 40%, the performance degradation mechanism was more related to Li ions being trapped in the SEI [328]. For different Si/Gr electrode structures, considering the evolution of porosity can help better understand the degradation of Si/Gr hybrid anodes. The weak constraint of the Si layer leads to a smaller decrease in porosity, resulting in better cell cycle performance [329]. This implies that Si/Gr systems, the optimal densification must balance mechanical accommodation for Si expansion with sufficient structural integrity for efficient charge transport.

To address the issues of high irreversible Li loss and differences in Li intercalation kinetics between the two phases in the first cycle of Si/Gr hybrid anodes, pre-lithiation has become a key means to improve their actual energy density and cycle stability. Available pre-lithiation strategies mainly fall into three categories: (i) electrochemical pre-lithiation, which achieves precise, controllable, and uniform pre-lithiation depth through partial Li intercalation in a half-cell system; (ii) chemical/spontaneous pre-lithiation (SCDL), which achieves rapid and scalable pre-lithiation through contact between the anode and metallic Li in the electrolyte; and (iii) source Li additive methods, such as PLMP, Li₃N, or Li₂O compounds, which gradually release Li ion within the electrode and are directly compatible with coating processes.

Each of these three methods has its advantages: electrochemical methods are suitable for precise control; spontaneous pre-lithiation processes are simple and suitable for large-scale manufacturing; and additive methods can achieve volumetric and mild pre-lithiation. In the Si/Gr system, the selection should be based on a comprehensive consideration of Si content, Si structure, electrode compaction density, and target ICE, in order to compensate for the initial formation loss of SEI, improve Si/Gr Li intercalation matching, and reduce the current segregation within the electrode caused by heterolithiation.

Unlike single Si or Gr anodes, the Si/Gr hybrid system exhibits significant material-specific Li distribution and migration behavior after pre-lithiation. Berhaut et al. [330] found that although spontaneous lithiation initially only causes highly localized lithiation in the contact area, after multiple cycles, the additional Li redistributes throughout the electrode, ultimately exhibiting uniform Si and Gr lithiation behavior. More importantly, additional Li is ultimately stored primarily in the Si phase, making Si a long-term Li reservoir to continuously compensate for Li loss caused by SEI

growth and structural evolution, thereby significantly improving capacity retention over thousands of cycles (1760 cycles~89%).

Frankenstein's work [289] demonstrated a unique "Transfer-Lithiation" mechanism in the Si/Gr electrode: even if the initial pre-lithiated Li is mainly located in Gr (LiC₆), during rest or cycling, Li spontaneously migrates from Gr to Si, manifesting as LiC₆ signal attenuation and Li_xSi enhancement. This migration is not self-discharge, but rather an internal localized battery effect driven by the chemical potential difference between Si and Gr, and significantly accelerated by Si structures such as thinner, more amorphous Si. These results indicate that in Si/Gr hybrid anodes, pre-lithiation not only compensates for Li loss but also drives Si to act as a "Li buffer", fundamentally improving the interface coupling and cycle stability of the Si/Gr system.

In Si/Gr hybrid anodes, the binder plays a critical role not only in providing mechanical adhesion but also in accommodating the pronounced heterogeneity in volumetric and electrochemical behavior between the two active phases, Si with up to 250–300% expansion and Gr with only ~10%. Consequently, binders in Si/Gr systems must simultaneously ensure strong interfacial adhesion to the Si surface, sufficient elasticity to buffer its large strain, and robust network integrity to preserve the Gr framework and electronic percolation. Carboxyl-functionalized polymers such as PAA [331, 332], CMC/SBR [333], and alginate [334] effectively anchor to the silica-rich surface via multi-point hydrogen or ionic bonding, while conductive [335] or dynamically cross-linked binders (e.g., TEGDA:PAA [336], CMC-PAA networks [337]) further stabilize particle–particle contacts by dissipating mechanical stress and maintaining electronic pathways during repeated cycling. Importantly, an appropriately engineered binder can also mitigate heterogeneous lithiation in Si/Gr electrodes by promoting structural coherence between the two phases, thereby reducing particle fracture, suppressing excessive SEI regeneration, and improving long-term capacity retention.

Due to the high volumetric expansion of Si compared to the minimal interlayer expansion of Gr, heterogeneous deformation occurs during lithiation, resulting in an uneven stress field and interfacial strain gradient. These mechanical mismatches lead to particle fracture, SEI rupture, and internal delamination, all of which contribute to capacity decay. Therefore, Si/Gr hybrid anodes require careful attention to the swelling behavior at the electrode level, as it is more directly related to battery performance. Related research indicates that anode porosity can buffer the expansion of pouch cells during the first half of charging, while a rigid 18650 casing causes a continuous decrease in anode porosity [338]. In situ expansion tests on Si/Gr||NMC622 pouch cells show expansion rates of 19.9%, 17.6%, and 16.1% under external pressures of 0.1, 0.5, and 1 MPa, respectively. External pressure can both limit anode expansion during lithiation and promote anode contraction during delithiation. Furthermore, a larger expansion was observed at an N/P ratio of 1.04 than at 1.11, with a total expansion of 10.1 μm compared to 8.5 μm at 1.11. [339] Although the battery swelling behavior is essentially caused by the expansion of Si, the actual electrode parameters still significantly affect the battery swelling behavior.

FIGURE 22 | Key parameters affecting energy density of Si/Gr anode-based LIBs. Reproduced with permission [36]. Copyright 2016, Springer Nature. Reproduced with permission [340]. Copyright 2025, Elsevier. Reproduced with permission [341]. Copyright 2024, Elsevier. Reproduced with permission [342]. Copyright 2019, Elsevier.

While the preceding sections have examined the individual effects from electrode level and cell design, like porosity/compaction density, N/P ratio, pre-lithiation strategies, electrode swelling, and binder chemistry, these factors do not act independently in practical Si/Gr-based cells. Instead, the achievable performance of a Si/Gr hybrid anode is governed by the combined interplay among these parameters, from materials design to electrode fabrication, battery assembly, and finally, the operational process (Figure 22), which together determine the usable energy density. As a result, assessing each parameter in isolation provides an incomplete view of the realistic performance boundary of Si/Gr electrodes.

To enable a more holistic and engineering-relevant comparison, we integrate these considerations into a unified “achievable energy–density” framework. This framework evaluates reported Si/Gr systems based on a consistent set of practically meaningful boundary conditions, namely areal capacity, compaction density, and N/P ratio, which collectively define the design window

in which high volumetric and gravimetric energy densities can be attained. Consolidated representative full-cell data from the literature (Table 7) are mapped onto this common basis, allowing direct cross-study comparison independent of material-specific metrics such as intrinsic capacity alone. By positioning diverse Si/Gr anode designs within this shared engineering parameter space, we identify the practical operating window where Si/Gr hybrids can contribute meaningfully to high-energy-density LIBs. This unified framework thus provides an essential bridge between material-level innovations and cell-level manufacturability considerations, offering a more realistic perspective on the deployment potential of Si/Gr hybrid anodes.

Overall, the available full-cell data indicate that Si/Gr hybrid anodes exhibit the most pronounced performance benefits when paired with Ni-rich NCM cathodes, where they deliver substantial energy–density gains, often approaching 40% improvement, while maintaining competitive cycle life under dynamic load profiles. However, the intrinsic activity of Si at low SOC renders Si/Gr

TABLE 7 | Representative Si/Gr anodes and corresponding full-cell configurations.

Anode (type/ formulation)	Electrode		Cathode (type/ formulation)	Electrolyte	N/P	Energy density (Wh kg ⁻¹)	Performance	Refs.
	compaction density (g cm ⁻³)	Thickness (μm)						
C/Si@MPC- G:CMC:SBR:SP = 95:2:2:1	1.6/—/21(P)/ 3.2		NMC622 :PVDF:SP = 96:2:2	1.3 M LiPF ₆ in EC/DEC:3/7+10%FEC	1.1	333 932 Wh L ⁻¹	790 Wh L ⁻¹ @ 100th /85%	[343]
N-SiO _x /C/Gr flake (968):PAA:AB = 8:1:1			NMC622 :PVDF:SP = 8:1:1	1.3 M LiPF ₆ in EC/DEC:1/1	Weight ratio = 1:3	413	115 mAh g ⁻¹ @ 150th @ 0.1 A g ⁻¹ /88.5%	[344]
Pre-lithiated-SiO _x /Gr (850):CMC+SBR:SP+KS- 6+SWCNT = 94.5:1.4+2.6:0.7+0.3+0.5	1.55/82/5.85 (N)/ 4.7		NCM811 :PVDF:SP + KS-6+ SWCNT = 96.5:0.8:0.6+0.3+0.3	1 M LiPF ₆ in EC/DMC:3/7+2% FEC +1%VC	1.12	—	7.082 Ah @ 250th / 83.33%	[345]
BSi/CNT@Gr (460):PAA:AB = 6:2:2	—/—/12(P)/ 2.16		LiNi _{0.76} Co _{0.09} Mn _{0.15} O ₂	1 M LiPF ₆ in EC/DEC:1/1+10%FEC	1.2	—	180 mAh g ⁻¹ @ 300th @ 1 C/≈82.5%	[346]
Si/Gr (495):PAA:AB = 6.4:1:1	1/15/3.8(N) 8.9(P)/ 3.2		NCM622 :PVDF:SP = 96:2:2	1 M LiPF ₆ in EC/DMC/DEC: 1/1/1+5% FEC	1.2	190	97.9% @ 300th @ 4C (fast charging)	[347]
Si@GNCC:PAA:SP = 8:1:1	—/—/—/3.52		LiNi _{0.815} Co _{0.185-x} Al _x O ₂ :PVDF:SP = 8:1:1	1 M LiPF ₆ in EC/DMC:1/1+5% FEC	1.2	395	66.2% @ 80th @ 200 mA g ⁻¹	[348]
Si/C(600) (94.5%)+CMC+SBR+CNT double-sided coating	1.5/113/46(P) 16(N)/ 9.04		NCM811 AM(96.94%):PVDF:SP+ CNT:oxalic acid	1 M LiPF ₆ in EC/DEC/EMC: 2/3/5+8%FEC	1.05	300	1–30th: -11.90 mAh /cycle 30–210th: -3.95 mAh /cycle 210–300th: -12.73 mAh /cycle	[349]
Si/g-C ₃ N ₄ /Gr (422):PAA:CB = 6.4:1:1	—/—/—/—		LiFePO ₄ :PVDF:SP = 8:1:1	1 M LiPF ₆ in DEC/EC/EMC:1/1/1+5% FEC +1% VC	1.2	470	96% @ 60th @ 1C	[350]
Pre-lithiated Si/GCNS:PAA:AB = 8:1:1	—/—/—/—		LiFePO ₄ :PVDF:SP = 8:1:1	1 M LiPF ₆ in EC/DMC/DEC: 1/1/1+5% FEC	1.1	460	89.8% @ 300th @ 1 Ag ⁻¹	[351]
Si@C/Gr (527):CMC+ SBR:SP = 96:1.5+1.5:1	1.6/43/6.9(N) 20(P)/3.16		LiCoO ₂ :PVDF:SP = 96:2:2	1.3 M LiPF ₆ in EC/EMC/DEC:3/5/2+ 10%FEC+0.5%VC	1.1	1825 Wh L ⁻¹	493.9 mAh cm ⁻³ @ 300th @ 1 C /78.1% electrode swelling ratio (19%)	[352]
Monodisperse Si and C nano spheres (3207):PAA:CB = 7:1:2	—/—/—/—/3.52		LiCoO ₂ provided by Temiz Energy Technologies	1 M LiPF ₆ in EC/DMC: 1/1	>1	850 Wh L ⁻¹	2.2 mAh cm ⁻² @ 100th @ 0.5C	[353]
Si/C(650):CMC+SBR:SP = 90:2.8+4.2:3	—/—/—/—/19.4(P)/—		LiCoO ₂ :PVDF:CMC+SBR:SP = 96:2:1.8+0.2	1 M LiPF ₆ in FEC/DEC: 1/3+1%PTCB	1.1	—	92.46% (1.08 Ah) @ 500th @ 1C	[354]

FIGURE 23 | (a) X-ray images of battery cells with different Si content before and after thermal runaway. Reproduced with permission [357]. Copyright 2024, Elsevier. (b) A fully assembled three-electrode pouch cell. Reproduced with permission [358]. Copyright 2025, IOP Publishing. (c) 3D renderings of the operando time series of the Gr-only (left) and Si/Gr (right) cell in vertical orientation. Reproduced with permission. [359] Copyright 2025, IOP Publishing. (d) Preparation of the 18650 cylindrical cell with enhanced micro-CT analysis. Reproduced with permission [360]. Copyright 2024, Elsevier. (e) Schematic illustration of XRD computed tomography using a μm -sized synchrotron beam. Reproduced with permission [361]. Copyright 2024, Elsevier.

systems particularly sensitive to deep discharge and sustained fast-charging, making cathode choices with higher operational voltage (e.g., NCM) more compatible than lower-voltage systems [355, 356]. In contrast, LFP and LCO cells show limited integration of Si/Gr anodes, largely due to their lower specific energy ceilings and reduced incentive to compensate cathode-side limitations through anode-side capacity enhancement. Taken together, the present comparisons suggest that Si/Gr anodes are best leveraged in high-energy NCM-based architectures, provided that SOC management and charging protocols are carefully optimized.

The increasing availability of full-cell diagnostic tools has enabled direct observation of the heterogeneous behaviors that emerge in Si/Gr hybrid anodes during practical operation. In pouch cells, in situ and operando X-ray radiography has proven particularly effective for visualizing how Si-induced swelling evolves across charge/discharge cycles. Hahn et al. [357] investigated that in pouch cells, the load capacity can be increased by up to 30%

with increasing Si content, but the thermal runaway reaction also becomes more severe. X-ray images of battery cells (Figure 23a) show that for Si-free samples, the density distribution on the battery surface is relatively uniform, while for Si-containing pouch cells, the surface is very irregular and contains high-density aggregates. Three-electrode pouch-cell configurations (Figure 23b) further allow separation of anode and cathode potentials, enabling correlation between local overpotential spikes and zones of accelerated mechanical distortion, SEI thickening, or impedance rise.

In cylindrical cells, advanced techniques such as X-ray computed tomography (CT), digital volume correlation (DVC), and internal displacement field mapping uncover radial and azimuthal gradients that are not accessible in planar geometries [358]. Bond et al. [359] used time-resolved synchrotron radiation CT to directly image the electrolyte flow in two commercial 18650 batteries during cycling. In the vertically placed batteries,

the Si/Gr battery exhibited a more pronounced phenomenon of electrolyte depletion at the top and electrolyte accumulation at the bottom (Figure 23c). Introducing micron-sized contrast-enhancing particles into the Si-based anode of an 18 650 cylindrical LIB significantly improves the performance of micro-CT imaging technology and effectively mitigates radiation damage [360]. The displacement field observed in the speckled battery clearly demonstrates the volume expansion of the electrode during charging cycles and the volume contraction during discharging cycles, with local displacements reaching up to 35 μm .

Furthermore, significant asymmetry and spatial heterogeneity are observed in the displacement field distribution along both radial and azimuth directions (Figure 23d). Holderle et al. [361] investigated cylindrical LIBs with varying Si contents, focusing on the structural response of active battery components during electrochemical cycling. X-ray diffraction CT using a micrometer-scale synchrotron radiation beam revealed localized structural degradation and lithiation inhomogeneities in high-Si-content batteries during cycling (Figure 23e). Complementary methods [362, 363], such as thermal mapping, fiber Bragg grating/strain-gauge monitoring, in situ dilatometry, neutron radiography, ultrasonic sensing, and acoustic emission, further enrich this full-cell diagnostic framework, offering a multidimensional view of how mechanical, chemical, and electrical heterogeneities co-evolve in practical battery cells.

Together, these methodologies bridge the gap between particle-level lithiation behavior and full-cell degradation signatures, enabling a system-level understanding of how Si/Gr anode heterogeneity manifests, intensifies, and ultimately governs the lifetime and safety of commercial cell formats.

8 | Summary and Outlook

Si/Gr hybrid anodes represent a compelling pathway to simultaneously achieve high capacity and stable cycling, combining the best features of Gr and Si. Nevertheless, their multiphase nature introduces intricate electrochemical, mechanical, and interfacial interactions that must be systematically addressed to realize practical implementation. Looking ahead, several research directions appear particularly promising.

- i. **Fundamental Mechanisms:** A deeper understanding of heterogeneous lithiation, interparticle current distribution, and SEI evolution across multiple length scales is essential. These phenomena govern not only the dynamic balance of capacity contributions from Si and Gr but also the onset of degradation processes. The integration of operando and in situ characterization with multiscale modeling will be indispensable for establishing a holistic picture of these coupled dynamics.
- ii. **Material-level optimization:** At the materials scale, tailoring both components is crucial. Rational design of Si with controlled morphology, robust surface coatings, and chemically stable interfaces can alleviate volume mismatch and mitigate fracture. In parallel, engineering the properties of Gr, such as particle size, crystallinity, and porosity, will be

vital for enhancing compatibility and providing a resilient framework to buffer Si expansion.

- iii. **Electrode-level engineering:** Beyond the intrinsic properties of individual components, electrode architecture plays a decisive role. Strategies such as tuning hybrid composition, employing gradient or hierarchical electrode designs, and developing advanced binders and electrolytes offer effective routes to balance capacity retention, mechanical integrity, and long-term stability.
- iv. **Methodological synergy:** Progress will further rely on combining complementary approaches. Coordinated use of advanced characterization techniques, finite-element simulations, and equivalent experimental setups can accelerate the translation of mechanistic insights into practical design principles, reducing the gap between fundamental studies and device-level applications.
- v. **Scalability and industrial relevance:** Finally, for Si/Gr hybrids to move beyond laboratory prototypes, scalability must be prioritized. This entails careful consideration of electrode density, manufacturability, cost, and cycling stability under industrially relevant formats and conditions. Addressing these aspects is critical to align scientific innovation with commercial viability.

In conclusion, Si/Gr hybrids embody both opportunity and complexity. By uniting mechanistic understanding with engineering innovation, the research community can pave the way for these hybrid anodes to evolve from a promising academic concept into a commercially viable component of high-energy, long-life LIBs.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The authors have nothing to report.

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